

Modelling of the acoustic streaming in periodic rigid porous structures using homogenization

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Abstract

The paper presents a new model of the acoustic streaming (AS) in rigid porous media. The modelling is based on the classical perturbation approach combined with the periodic homogenization. The first one enables to linearize the Navier-Stokes equations for a barotropic fluid using the decomposition into the first and the second order subproblems governing the fluid dynamics in the rigid period scaffolds. The acoustic wave captured by the first order problem provides the Reynolds stress which appears in the second order problem as the streaming source term. Both the subproblems are treated by the homogenization resulting in the dynamic Darcy flow equations. Using spectral analysis of the characteristic microscopic dynamic Stokes flow and the associated spectral decomposition of the responses, the dynamic permeability is derived and also the driving force for the time-averaged permanent flow is evaluated. The AS can be observed at both the macroscopic and the microscopic levels. While the acoustics-driven microflows are observed for any microstructure, the macroscopic AS depends on the porous microstructure geometry, its nonsymmetry and boundary conditions. For porous particulate structures, the forces and force moments acting on the suspended particles are computed and the influence of the wave frequency and geometrical features is examined. All these effects are illustrated using 2D examples of periodic porous microstructures.

Keywords: acoustic streaming, porous media, acoustic waves, periodic microstructures, homogenization, perturbation analysis, Navier-Stokes equations

1. Introduction

Acoustic streaming (AS) refers to a steady fluid flow generated as the secondary effect of acoustic waves propagating in a viscous fluid. This phenomenon enjoys steadily increasing attention in the scientific field of ultrasound treatment as one of the major principles for contactless micro-macro manipulation with vast applications in biochemistry, medical

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therapy involving drug delivery and sonoporation Wu (2018); Wang et al. (2023). The acoustic metamaterials and the use of acoustic waves in biotechnologies involving porous structures present important field of applications for the use of the AS in porous structures, involving both soft materials, such as tissues, and almost rigid structures. Namely this latter kind of periodic porous materials is considered in the present study. The principal goal of our paper is to provide a rigorous homogenization-based modelling of the AS in these structures. Although numerical examples are limited to 2D structures, the presented results show the importance to respect particular geometries of the porous structures presented as periodically distributed obstacles (suspensions of particles, *cf.* Nadal and Lauga (2014)).

Physically, AS appears as the consequence of inhomogeneities in the viscous flow caused by non-zero divergence of the Reynolds stress associated with acoustic fluctuations, or due to vibrating fluid-solid interface in the response of surface acoustic waves in the solid phase. In the latter case, the phenomenon observed in the viscous fluid boundary layers is called the Rayleigh streaming, while in the bulk fluid it is classified as the Eckart streaming associated with high frequencies. Mathematical modelling of the AS was originated by Lord Rayleigh at the end of the 19th century (Rayleigh, 1884, 1892). Compared to the classic linear model of the fluid acoustics arising from the Euler equations with neglected advection term leading to the Helmholtz equation governing the acoustic waves, the AS flow induced by the acoustic waves emerges due to the dissipation and the nonlinearity arising from the advection term constituting the fluid particle acceleration. Its importance depends on the Reynolds, Péclet and Strouhal numbers respecting the effects of dissipation, advection and the finite size amplitude of the acoustic waves.

Major pioneering contributions to the AS analysis are due to Nyborg and Lighthill (Nyborg, 1953; Lighthill, 1978) who established the fundamental framework for the nonlinear acoustic wave treatment using the perturbation theory which leads to the decomposition of the AS model in two parts: the first one describes the acoustic waves and provides the AS source involved in the second part which describes the AS as a time averaged flow. Alternative approaches are based on the WKBJ (Wentzel-Kramers-Brillouin-Jeffreys) approximation Chini et al. (2014); Michel and Chini (2019), such that by introducing two time scales, slow temporal evolution of the AS due to acoustic wave modulation can be captured.

With recent intensive development of acoustics-based devices and technologies, the AS phenomenon becomes one of the most important tools for micromanipulation in microfluidics and biotechnologies, see *e.g.* Mohanty et al. (2020); Nadal and Lauga (2014); Raghavan (2018); Wu (2018); Maramizonouz et al. (2021). However, mathematical modelling of the related processes remains rather a challenge according to a few works rigorously treating this topic. As pointed out in Manor (2021), where a comprehensive survey of papers devoted to the acoustic waves related fluxes, the AS in the context of porous media represented by microtubes has been considered since the very early works by Kirchhoff, (Kirchhoff, 1868). Although the wave propagation in porous media were studied by the theory of porous media, see *e.g.* Allard and Atalla (2009) and, in parallel, using the asymptotic analysis based homogenization Ferrín and Mikelić (2003); Rohan (2013); Rohan and

Naili (2020); Rohan and Cimrman (2021), the most remarkable contributions to the influence on the generated secondary “steady” flow have appeared rather recently Panhuis et al. (2009); Valverde (2015); Valverde and Durán-Olivencia (2014); Raghavan (2018); Manor (2021); Price et al. (2023). Arrays of cylinders Valverde (2015), or tubes Panhuis et al. (2009) were considered while neglecting the solid phase compliance. The numerical study of the AS effect studied for a variety of channel shapes, as reported in Červenka and Bednařík (2016), indicates the importance of the porosity design.

In spite of a serious research of particular phenomena associated with the acoustic streaming effects, *e.g.* Wu (2018), considering simultaneously several coupling phenomena, some combinations and namely aspects of the structure periodic heterogeneity have been overlooked.

The paper is devoted to the acoustic streaming (AS) in periodic porous structures constituted by rigid, or elastic scaffolds saturated by Newtonian barotropic fluid. The AS in porous media has been studied only very rarely so far in spite of many potential applications, such as tissue engineering, or thermoacoustic engines. We focus on analytical and numerical methods developed to solve efficiently the acoustic streaming problem in the homogenized porous medium.

Only very limit body of literature devoted to the topic of modelling the AS phenomenon in porous media can be found, see Raghavan (2018) for a comprehensive survey. Arrays of cylinders representing granular flows exposed to the AS was studied in Valverde (2015); Valverde and Durán-Olivencia (2014) also using numerical modelling. Bundles of parallel channels slowly varying along their axis were considered in Panhuis et al. (2009) in the context of thermoacoustic devices, while neglecting the solid phase compliance. The most relevant works Manor (2021); Price et al. (2023) use the perturbation-based splitting Nyborg (1953) are concerned with a simplified treatment of the acoustic waves using a “homogeneous approximation” of the porous medium constituted by the fluid and an elastic solid having the same acoustic impedance. The focus is on the secondary effects associated with the generated flows reflecting the fluid-structure interaction. In Manor (2021), the AS in porous media was investigated using a structural tensor (being inspired by saturated packed granular media, Morse (1952)) representing bundles of parallel tubes with varying orientation, whereby various cases according to the penetration depth related to the pore size were treated. The volume-averaging technique was applied in Price et al. (2023) to describe ultrasound generated AS in soft porous media.

The frequency ω of the acoustic waves inducing the AS in pores as related to the penetration depth $\delta_A = \sqrt{2\mu/\rho_0\omega}$ which is influenced by the fluid viscosity μ . In this respect, there is a significant difference of the AS response observed in deformable poroelastic continua-when compared to porous media with rigid sold skeleton.

Acoustic wave propagation in the fluid-saturated porous media has been studied intrusively since the seminal works by Biot (Biot, 1941, 1955). Besides the phenomenological approaches, see *e.g.* Carcione (2014), the homogenization method based on the asymptotic analysis with respect to the scale parameter has been employed in many works under various assumptions on the micromodel relevant to the heterogeneous period microstructures, applied in the case of quasi-static problems Burrige and Keller (1982). The two scale

convergence has been applied to treat acoustic properties of the poroelastic medium saturated by viscous fluids in Clopeau et al. (2001), reporting the acoustics of an in-viscid fluid Ferrín and Mikelić (2003). A number of works have been devoted to the upscaling of heterogeneous Biot model Mielke and Rohan (2013); Nguyen et al. (2016). Modelling waves in double porosity media was considered in Auriault and Boutin (1994) by a two-level formal homogenization. Another approach based on the homogenization with a strong heterogeneity scaling unseats related to the permeability was used in Rohan (2013) assuming a rigid skeleton Nguyen et al. (2016). For deformable double porosity media, the wave dispersion was analyzed using the same homogenization preach in Rohan et al. (2018), further generalized in Rohan et al. (2024). Issues of a small compressibility of barotropic fluids and the related mathematical aspects of the micromodel linearization was studied in Gilbert and Panchenko (2004) also in the context of acoustics in disordered porous media. Acoustics in elastic scaffold’s perfused by viscous fluids was treated in Rohan and Naili (2020); Rohan et al. (2021) where also the advection phenomenon of the Navier-Stokes equations was accounted for, leading to a flow-dependent dynamic permeability tensor.

Novelty and contribution. Up to our knowledge, this paper is the first one where a two-scale model describing the AS phenomenon in periodic porous structures is derived using the homogenization approach. The modelling is based on the asymptotic analysis with respect to size of the microstructures of and the classical perturbation approach Nyborg (1953) with respect to a small parameter proportional to the inverse Stroll number. This yields the first and the second order sub-problem enabling to linearize the Navier-Stokes (N-S) equations governing the barotropic viscous fluid dynamics in pores of a periodic structure. Subsequent treatment by the asymptotic homogenization leads to a two scale problem where the macroscopic model of the porous medium describes the acoustic streaming (AS) phenomenon. Although the homogenization of the first order problem describing the acoustic waves in the rigid porous structures has been treated in the literature, *e.g.* Venegas et al. (2021); Rohan (2013), *cf.* Rohan and Cimrman (2021); Rohan and Lukeš (2024), we report the main steps of the asymptotic analysis and the “micro-macro” decomposition using a spectral decomposition of the so-called micro-flow problems. This yields the effective dynamic permeability introduced in terms of the injunction’s and eigenvalues of the Stokes problem in the representative cell. The same approach is employed to upscale the second order sub-problem. The AS velocity is given by the macroscopic pressure governed by the effective Darcy flow driven by the divergence of the Reynolds stresses. These are computed by a time averaging of the 1st order time-harmonic solution of the acoustic problem in the upscaled medium described by the dynamic Darcy law.

The rest of the paper is organized, as follows. The model describing the flow driven by the acoustic waves in pores of rigid periodic structures is introduced in Section 2, where the linearization based on the perturbation analysis is established. The decomposed problem governing the AS phenomenon is treated using the homogenization method in Section 3, leading to the two-scale models of the acoustic waves and the superimposed AS. Numerical simulations of the AS phenomenon in rigid porous media are reported in Section 4, where the influence of the microstructure geometry is illustrated using 2D example’s. Technical

issues employed in the main part of the paper and the reduced 1D modelling of the AS in a finite layer and infinite medium are postponed in Appendix A and Appendix B, respectively.

Notation. Specific symbols used are explained throughout the paper. A point position in a Cartesian frame is specified by $x = (x_1, \dots, x_3) \in \mathbb{R}^d$, $d = 2, 3$. $\partial\Omega$ refers to the boundary of a domain Ω . In the context of the two-scale homogenization, x denotes the global (“macroscopic”) coordinates, while the “local” coordinates $y = (y_1, \dots, y_3) \in Y \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ describe positions within the representative unit cell Y . The boldface notation for vectors $\mathbf{a} = (a_i)$ and second-order tensors $\mathbf{b} = (b_{ij})$ is used. The gradient, divergence and Laplace operators are denoted by ∇ , $\nabla \cdot$ and ∇^2 , respectively. When these operators have a subscript referring to the space variable, it is for indicating that the operator acts relatively at this space variable, for instance $\nabla_y = (\partial_i^y) = (\partial/\partial y_i)$. The symbol dot ‘ \cdot ’ denotes the scalar product between two vectors and the symbol colon ‘ $:$ ’ stands for scalar (inner) product of two second-order tensors, *e.g.* $\mathbf{A} : \mathbf{B} = A_{ij}B_{ij} = \text{tr}[\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{B}] = A_{ki}B_{kj}\delta_{ij}$, where $\text{tr}[\star]$ is the trace of a tensor and superscript T in \star^T is the transposition operator. Operator \otimes designates the tensor product between two vectors, *e.g.* $\mathbf{a} \otimes \mathbf{v} = (a_i v_j)$. Standard notations for functional spaces are adhered. The normal vectors on a boundary of domains are denoted by \mathbf{n} . The following standard functional spaces are used: by $L^2(\Omega)$ we refer to square integrable functions defined in an open bounded domain Ω ; by $H^1(\Omega)$ we mean the Sobolev space $W^{1,2}(\Omega) \subset L^2(\Omega)$ formed by square integrable functions including their first generalized derivatives. In analogy, spaces $L^2(Y)$ and $H^1(Y)$ are related to domain Y . Bold notation is used to denote spaces of vector-valued functions, *e.g.* $\mathbf{H}^1(\Omega)$; by subscript $\#$ we refer to the Y -periodic functions. The notation with “tilde” and/or “bar” over, or under symbols can have various meanings which are explained through the text and are clear within the particular context. By \tilde{f} , the image of the Laplace transform of a function $f(t)$ with respect to time t is denoted, *i.e.* $\mathcal{L}\{f(t)\} \mapsto \tilde{f}(\lambda)$; in analogy, $\underset{\circ}{f}$ means the Fourier transform of $f(t)$ (as employed in Appendix B.2). Finally, the use of α and β has different meaning depending on the context at different parts of the paper, but a confusion is unlikely while reading thoroughly.

2. Fluctuating flows in porous rigid structure

In this section we introduce the fluid dynamics problem imposed in pores of a rigid skeleton constituted by a connected domain (the scaffolds), or by suspension of rigid immobile particles. Then the problem is decomposed into the so called 1st and the 2nd order problems using the successive approximations based on the perturbation analysis.

2.1. Fluid flow problem

We consider an open domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, $d = 2, 3$, bounded $\partial\Omega$ in which scaffolds of a porous medium are placed, occupying a domain $\Omega_s \subset \Omega$, such that the fluid is situated in the pores $\Omega_f = \Omega \setminus \overline{\Omega_s}$ bounded by $\partial\Omega_f$, whereby $\Gamma_s = \Gamma_{f_s} = \partial\Omega_f \cap \partial\Omega_s$ is the interface. To

introduce the boundary conditions (BCs), we consider the following split of the boundaries:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial\Omega_f &= \partial_\sigma\Omega_f \cup \partial_v\Omega_f \cup \Gamma_{fs} , \\ \text{where } \partial_\sigma\Omega_f &\equiv \partial_\sigma\Omega \text{ and } \partial_v\Omega_f \equiv \partial_v\Omega . \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

In this paper, we treat flows and acoustic responses in barotropic viscous fluid characterized by the reference speed of sound, c_0 , the reference density ρ_0 , and the shear and bulk viscosities, μ and ζ , respectively. The total fluid stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^f = (\sigma_{ij}^f)$ is given by $\sigma_{ij}^f = -p^f\delta_{ij} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{ij}^{visc}$, depending on the pressure p^f , and on the fluid velocity $\mathbf{v}^f = (v_i^f)$. The latter is involved in the viscous part of the stress, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{visc} = \mathbb{D}^f \nabla \mathbf{v}^f$, being expressed in terms of the tensor $\mathbb{D}^f = (D_{ijkl}^f)$ given by $D_{ijkl}^f = \mu(\delta_{ik}\delta_{jl} + \delta_{il}\delta_{jk}) + (\zeta - 2/3\mu)\delta_{ij}\delta_{kl}$. Hence, $\sigma_{ij}^f = -p^f\delta_{ij} + D_{ijkl}^f 1/2(\partial_j v_i^f + \partial_i v_j^f)$. Since the perturbations are assumed to be small enough, we neglect any influence of the temperature fluctuations on the viscosity. The fluid flow in a rigid porous structures is described by the triplet $(\mathbf{v}^f, p^f, \rho^f)$ satisfying

$$\begin{aligned} \rho^f \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v}^f + \mathbf{v}^f \cdot \nabla \mathbf{v}^f \right) &= -\nabla p^f + \nabla \cdot \mathbb{D}^f \nabla \mathbf{v}^f + \mathbf{f}^f , \quad \text{in } \Omega_f , \\ \frac{\partial \rho^f}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho^f \mathbf{v}^f) &= 0 , \quad \text{in } \Omega_f , \\ p^f &= c_0^2 \rho^f + c_0 c'_0 (\rho^f)^2 + o(|\rho^f|^3) , \quad c'_0 = \frac{d c_0(\rho_0)}{d \rho} , \quad (2.2) \\ \mathbf{v}^f &= \mathbf{0} , \quad \text{on } \Gamma_s , \\ \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}^f &= \mathbf{g}^f , \quad \text{on } \partial_\sigma \Omega_f , \\ \mathbf{v}^f &= \mathbf{v}^\partial , \quad \text{on } \partial_v \Omega_f , \end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{f}^f and \mathbf{g}^f are the body and traction forces, respectively, and velocity \mathbf{v}^∂ is prescribed on $\partial_v \Omega_f$. In our study we consider vanishing volume forces, so that we put $\mathbf{f}^f = \mathbf{0}$. Due to the barotropic law, p^f is introduced using the Taylor expansion, whereby $c_0 = \sqrt{p_0/\rho_0}$ for given reference pressure p_0 and ρ_0 .

2.2. Problem decomposition using the successive approximations

To distinguish the phenomenon of the acoustic streaming, pursuing the standard approach of the perturbation analysis, we consider the following approximation of the flow response expressed by terms of different order with respect to the small parameter $\alpha \approx v_0/c_0$, where v_0 is a characteristic flow velocity, $v_0 \ll c_0$, such that the Mach number is very small,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{v}^f &= \alpha \mathbf{v}_1 + \alpha^2 \mathbf{v}_2 + \dots , \\ p^f &= p_0 + \alpha p_1 + \alpha^2 p_2 + \dots , \\ \rho^f &= \rho_0 + \alpha \rho_1 + \alpha^2 \rho_2 + \dots , \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

where p_0, ρ_0 are assumed to be positive constants and, in the generic sense, a_k denotes k -th order in α approximation of the quantity a . Moreover, we assume that the first order a_1

quantity is harmonic in time with the T -period time. Further, due to the 1st order problem linearity, we may confine to harmonic responses function given by the angular frequency $\omega = 2\pi/T$.

We shall use the time average of a quantity a_k and of its time derivative; for $n \in \mathbb{N}_+$

$$\bar{a}_k^n(t) = \frac{1}{nT} \int_t^{t+nT} a_k(\tau) d\tau, \quad \frac{d\bar{a}_k^n}{dt}(t) = \overline{\frac{da_k}{dt}}^n(t), \quad (2.4)$$

whereby for $n = 1$, *i.e.* the one-period average, we use the notation $\bar{a}_k \equiv \bar{a}_k^1$. For the nT -periodic functions a_1 , clearly $d/dt(\bar{a}_1^n) = 0$.

As the next step, the 1st and 2nd order problems with respect to α are distinguished. Upon substituting expansions (2.3) in the flow model (2.2) and collecting there the terms of order $O(\alpha^1)$, (2.2), and neglecting all those of order higher than $O(\alpha^1)$, we get equations governing the time harmonic responses $(\mathbf{v}_1, p_1, \rho_1)$, thus, the *Acoustic Wave Propagation (AWP)*,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho_1 + \rho_0 \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_1 &= 0, \\ \rho_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v}_1 + \nabla p_1 &= \mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{v}_1 + (\mu/3 + \zeta) \nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_1), \\ p_1 &= c_0^2 \rho_1. \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

At the second order, *i.e.* the terms $O(\alpha^2)$, (2.2) yields the equations of the *Acoustic Streaming Flow (ASF)*,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho_2 + \nabla \cdot (\rho_1 \mathbf{v}_1) + \rho_0 \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_2 &= 0, \\ \rho_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v}_2 + \rho_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v}_1 + \rho_0 (\mathbf{v}_1 \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v}_1 + \nabla p_2 &= \mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{v}_2 + (\mu/3 + \zeta) \nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_2), \\ p_2 &= c_0^2 \rho_2 + c_0 c_0' (\rho_1)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

These equalities hold provided terms of order higher than α^2 are neglected and (2.5) is satisfied.

To capture the AS effect, we are interested in the time averaged response of the 2nd order problem arising from (2.6). Note that the time average over a multiple of period T applied in (2.5) makes it vanish. We employ the following auxiliary formula derived using the continuity equation (2.5)₁,

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \overline{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_1 \mathbf{v}_1)} = \rho_1 \overline{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v}_1} + \mathbf{v}_1 \overline{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho_1}, \\ \Rightarrow \overline{\rho_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v}_1} &= \overline{\rho_0 \mathbf{v}_1 (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_1)}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

This enables to express the term $\overline{\rho_1 \partial_t \mathbf{v}_1}$ in the time averaged (2.6), which now yields

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \bar{\rho}_2 + \rho_0 \nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{v}}_2 &= -\nabla \cdot \overline{(\rho_1 \mathbf{v}_1)}, \\ \rho_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \bar{\mathbf{v}}_2 + \nabla \bar{p}_2 - \mu \nabla^2 \bar{\mathbf{v}}_2 + (\mu/3 + \zeta) \nabla (\nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{v}}_2) &= -\rho_0 \left(\overline{(\mathbf{v}_1 \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v}_1} + \overline{\mathbf{v}_1 (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_1)} \right), \\ \bar{p}_2 &= c_0^2 \bar{\rho}_2 + c_0 c_0' \overline{(\rho_1)^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

Later, in Section 3.3, we drop the “over-bar” notation indicating the time average for the sake of the notation brevity, so that all 2nd order unknown fields are considered being time-averaged.

Remark 1. For the decomposed form (2.5)-(2.6) of the acoustic streaming problem BCs are needed when Ω_f is a bounded domain (later we consider infinite media, i.e. Ω_f is infinite). We assume $\partial_\nu \Omega_f \equiv \emptyset$ and consider the following BCs in the two subproblems:

BCs for the 1st order problem – AWP. We can prescribe conditions in accordance with (2.2), whereby $\partial_\sigma \Omega_f \subset \partial\Omega$ is the “external boundary” of the pores,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{v}_1 &= \mathbf{0}, \quad \text{on } \Gamma_{fs}, \\ \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 &= -P_1^\partial \mathbf{n}, \quad \text{on } \partial_\sigma \Omega_f. \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

BCs for the 2nd order problem – ASF. We can consider the following BCs,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{v}_2 &= \mathbf{0}, \quad \text{on } \Gamma_{fs}, \\ \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_2 &= -P_2^\partial \mathbf{n}, \quad \text{on } \partial_\sigma \Omega_f, \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

where P_k^∂ , $k = 1, 2$ are the prescribed pressure values.

Figure 1: Periodic porous structures: the solid part can be connected (right: section of a 3D structure), or disconnected (left), always the case in 2D). Note $\varepsilon \approx \ell$ for the macroscopic characteristic size $L \approx 1$.

3. Homogenization of the decomposed acoustic model

We consider periodic porous structures with the characteristic pore scale being proportional to a small parameter $\varepsilon = \ell/L$ defined by the ratio of the micro- and macroscopic characteristic lengths, denoted by ℓ and L , respectively, see Fig. 1. In acoustic problems, L is typically given by the wave length. The homogenization procedure applied to derive an effective model of the two-phase medium consists in the asymptotic analysis $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ of the micro-models (2.5) and (2.6) presented above. To this purpose, in what follows, all the unknowns and model parameters depending on the scale are labeled by superscript ε .

3.1. Periodic microstructure

A periodic structure of channels Ω_f^ε is generated as a periodic lattice by the representative channel segment $\mathcal{Z}_f^\varepsilon \subset \mathcal{Z}^\varepsilon$ with $\mathcal{Z}^\varepsilon = \prod_{i=1}^3]0, \varepsilon \ell^i[$, being the representative periodic cell, see Fig. 1. The complementary solid part $\mathcal{Z}_s^\varepsilon = \mathcal{Z}^\varepsilon \setminus \mathcal{Z}_f^\varepsilon$ generates the solid skeleton occupying domain $\Omega_s^\varepsilon = \Omega \setminus \Omega_f^\varepsilon$. Obviously, Ω_f^ε is assumed to be connected domain, whereas Ω_s^ε can be disconnected, being constituted by mutually separated and periodically distributed obstacles $\mathcal{Z}_s^\varepsilon \subset \mathcal{Z}^\varepsilon$; such a situation necessarily arises when dealing with 2D problems.

The pores are bounded by the fluid-solid interface $\Gamma_{fs}^\varepsilon = \partial\Omega_s^\varepsilon \cap \partial\Omega_f^\varepsilon$ and by an external surface $\partial_{\text{ext}}\Omega_f^\varepsilon = \partial\Omega \cap \partial\Omega_f^\varepsilon$. For the purpose of the homogenization we consider the “unit periodic cell” $Y = \varepsilon^{-1}\mathcal{Z}^\varepsilon$ and its subparts $Y_d = \varepsilon^{-1}\mathcal{Z}_d^\varepsilon$, $d = s, f$ introduced by the homothety, such that $Y = Y_f \cup Y_s \cup \Gamma$, where $\Gamma = \partial Y_f \cap \partial Y_s$.

Correspondingly to the no-slip condition $\mathbf{v}^\varepsilon = \mathbf{0}$ on Γ_{fs}^ε , the fluid viscosity is considered as proportional to the pore size, or the pore cross-section, see also Remark 2, (ii) for the physical context. The internal characteristic length is introduced due to scaling of the viscosity by ε^2 , *i.e.* with constants $\bar{\mu}, \bar{\zeta} > 0$,

$$\mu^\varepsilon = \varepsilon^2 \bar{\mu}, \quad \zeta^\varepsilon = \varepsilon^2 \bar{\zeta}. \quad (3.1)$$

This holds for flow problems, when the advection acceleration can be neglected, see *e.g.* Al-laïre (1992); Hornung (1997); Clopeau et al. (2001). However, if fluid inertia is concerned, $\mu^\varepsilon = \varepsilon^\beta \bar{\mu}$, whereby exponent $\beta > 0$ is to be determined, *cf.* Chen et al. (2001). Other parameters describing the fluid are considered as constants, namely c_0, c'_0, ρ_0 and p_0 .

The homogenization procedure is presented below formally, without giving convergence proofs, however, the derivations of the limit equations can be followed. We use the standard notation; for any $D \subset Y$ we abbreviate $\mathcal{J}_D = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_D$; note that usually one may chose \bar{y}^i , $i = 1, 2, 3$, such that $|Y| = 1$. The following spaces are employed: $H_{\#}^1(Y_f) \subset H^1(Y_f)$ containing only Y -periodic functions. In analogy, a space of Y -periodic vector-valued functions is denoted by $\mathbf{H}_{\#}^1(Y_f)$, so that the following space is needed to introduce fluid velocities,

$$\mathbf{H}_{\#0}^1(Y_f) = \{\mathbf{v} \in \mathbf{H}_{\#}^1(Y_f) \mid \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{0} \text{ on } \partial Y_f \setminus \partial Y\}. \quad (3.2)$$

In the next two sections, homogenized problems will be derived for the 1st and the 2nd order problems introduced by equations (2.5) and (2.6), respectively, which are imposed in

the periodic porosity Ω_f^ε . It is worth to recall that the periodic unfolding methods enables to use the standard means of convergence in Hilbert spaces defined in the unfolded domain $\Omega \times Y$. Here we pursue the formal method of asymptotic expansion, since the rigorous treatment beyond the scope of this paper, although it can be adapted *e.g.* from Rohan and Naili (2020).

3.2. Homogenization of the AWP problem

For the problem arising from (2.5), the unfolded solutions $(\mathbf{v}_1^\varepsilon, p_1^\varepsilon, \rho_1^\varepsilon)$ are expressed in terms of truncated expansions with respect to ε ,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{T}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{v}^\varepsilon(x, t)) &= \varepsilon^{1/2} \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0(x, y, t) , \\ \mathcal{T}_\varepsilon(p_1^\varepsilon(x, t)) &= \varepsilon^{1/2} (p_1^0(x, t) + \varepsilon p_1^1(x, y, t)) , \\ \mathcal{T}_\varepsilon(\rho_1^\varepsilon(x, t)) &= \varepsilon^{1/2} (\rho_1^0(x, t) + \varepsilon \rho_1^1(x, y, t)) ,\end{aligned}\tag{3.3}$$

where $\mathcal{T}_\varepsilon(\cdot)$ is the unfolding operator introduced in Cioranescu et al. (2008), *cf.* Cioranescu et al. (2018). As the result of viscosity scaling (3.1) and due to the nonslip condition $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_2 = \mathbf{0}$ on Γ^ε , velocity \mathbf{v}_2^0 depends on y , see *e.g.* Allaire (1992); Cioranescu et al. (2018); Rohan and Naili (2020).

The scaling by $\varepsilon^{1/2}$ has no effects on the homogenization of the linear problem (2.5), however, it is needed to retain the acoustic streaming source term in (2.8) when $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. Note that the expansions for p_1^ε and ρ_1^ε are consistent by virtue of the barotropic approximation (2.5)₃. All the two-scale functions are Y -periodic in the second variable y and for almost all $t > 0$

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0(\cdot, t), \hat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}} &\in L^2(\Omega; \mathbf{H}_{\#0}^1(Y_f)) , \\ p_1^1(\cdot, t), q^1 &\in L^2(\Omega; H_{\#}^1(Y_f)) , \quad p_1^0(\cdot, t), q^0 \in H^1(\Omega) .\end{aligned}\tag{3.4}$$

Note that the no-slip conditions of $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}$ on Γ are imposed due to the space $\mathbf{H}_{\#0}^1(Y_f)$ introduced in (3.2).

Substitution of (3.3) in (2.5)₁ yields

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_1^0 + \varepsilon \rho_1^1) + \rho_0 (\nabla_x + \varepsilon^{-1} \nabla_y) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 = 0 ,\tag{3.5}$$

so that at order $o(\varepsilon^{-1})$ and $o(\varepsilon^0)$ we get respectively

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla_y \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 &= 0 , \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho_1^0 + \rho_0 \nabla_x \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 &= 0 .\end{aligned}\tag{3.6}$$

At order $o(\varepsilon^0)$, the momentum eq. (2.5)₂ with (2.5)₃ and (3.3) yields

$$\rho_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 + c_0^2 (\nabla_x \rho_1^0 + \nabla_y \rho_1^1) - (\bar{\mu} \nabla_y^2 \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 + (\bar{\mu}/3 + \bar{\zeta}) \nabla_y (\nabla_y \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0)) = 0 ,\tag{3.7}$$

where the last term vanishes due to (3.6)₁ imposing the local incompressibility.

As the next step of the homogenization, it is conventional to introduce the local characteristic subproblems which can be solved independently of the macroscopic functions. Due to the linearity of (3.7), its solution $(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0, p_1^1)$ can be parameterized by the macroscopic pressure gradient, $\partial_k^x p_1^0$. However, since the two-scale functions are coupled with the macroscopic ones also in time, the standard multiplicative split can be introduced only provided the Laplace transformation $\mathcal{L}\{f(t)\} \mapsto \tilde{f}(\lambda)$, is applied in (3.7). By virtue of the characteristic responses $(\hat{\mathbf{w}}^k, \hat{\pi}^k)$, $k = 1, \dots, d$, satisfying

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 = -\lambda \hat{\mathbf{w}}^k \partial_k^x p_1^0, \quad p_1^1 = c_0^2 \rho_1^1 = -\lambda \hat{\pi}^k \partial_k^x p_1^0, \quad (3.8)$$

the autonomous local subproblems extracted from (3.7) can be identified, see *e.g.* the treatment of the wave propagation in perfused porous media Rohan and Naili (2020). In this paper, instead of using the decomposition (3.8) directly, we proceed by a different approach based on the spectral decomposition applied also for the functions transformed by $\mathcal{L}\{ \}$.

3.2.1. Spectral decomposition and characteristic solutions

We apply the Laplace transformation to the weak formulation of the local problem arising from (3.7) and (3.6)₁, such that $(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0, p_1^1)$ satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda \rho_0 \int_{Y_f} \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 \cdot \hat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}} + \int_{Y_f} \hat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}} \cdot \nabla_y p_1^1 + \int_{Y_f} \bar{\mu} \nabla_y \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 : \nabla_y \hat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}} &= - \int_{Y_f} \hat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}} \cdot \nabla_x p_1^0, \\ \int_{Y_f} q^1 \nabla_y \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

for all $\hat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}} \in \mathbf{H}_{\#0}^1(Y_f)$ and $q^1 \in L^2(Y_f)$. Note that the Y -periodicity of all y -dependent functions and the nonslip velocity on the walls Γ has been employed.

Further we shall use the bilinear form related to the dissipation power and the inner product

$$\begin{aligned} a_f(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) &= \bar{\mu} \int_{Y_f} \nabla_y \mathbf{u} : \nabla_y \mathbf{v}, \\ \langle p, q \rangle_{Y_f} &= \int_{Y_f} pq, \quad \text{where} \quad \int_{Y_f} = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_{Y_f}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

The spectral decomposition of the Stokes flow problem will be employed to express the characteristic responses of the local problems at both the 1st and the 2nd order subproblems, see (2.5) and (2.6). To this aim, the following eigenvalue problem is solved. Find $(\mathbf{w}^r, \pi^r, \eta_r) \in \mathbf{H}_{\#0}^1(Y_f) \times L^2(Y_f) \times \mathbb{R}$ satisfying

$$\begin{aligned} a_f(\mathbf{w}^r, \mathbf{v}) - \langle \pi^r, \nabla_y \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_{Y_f} &= \eta_r \rho_0 \langle \mathbf{w}^r, \mathbf{v} \rangle_{Y_f}, \quad \forall \mathbf{v} \in \mathbf{H}_{\#0}^1(Y_f), \\ \langle q, \nabla_y \cdot \mathbf{w}^r \rangle_{Y_f} &= 0, \quad \forall q \in L^2(Y_f), \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

such that

$$\langle \mathbf{w}^r, \mathbf{w}^r \rangle_{Y_f} = 1. \quad (3.12)$$

It is worth noting that the eigenvalues η_r depend on $\bar{\mu}$ and ρ_0 , while the eigenfunctions do not.

Remark 2. (i) If the fluid is spatially homogeneous, thus, μ and ρ are constants, one may proceed by the spectral decomposition based on the eigenvalues $\tilde{\eta}_r$ satisfying (3.11) with formally putting $\rho_0 = 1$ and $\bar{\mu} = 1$. Then, for a given physical values ρ_0 and $\bar{\mu}$, the right eigenvalues are given by $\eta_r = \tilde{\eta}_r \bar{\mu} / \rho_0$. (ii) In this, context, for a homogeneous fluid, one may pass to a rescaled model for which the spectrum $\{\tilde{\eta}_r\}$ applies and, correspondingly, the time is rescaled by the characteristic time $t_c = \rho_0 / \bar{\mu} = \varepsilon^2 \rho_0 / \mu^{\text{phys}}$, thus, being related to the spatial scale ε by virtue of (3.1) where $\mu^{\text{phys}} \equiv \mu^\varepsilon$ is the physical value.

Due to the ellipticity of the bilinear form $a_f(\cdot, \cdot)$ functions \mathbf{w}^r, π^r are real-valued and $\eta_r \geq 0$ are real for any $r = 1, 2, \dots$. Moreover, $\eta_r \rho_0 / \bar{\mu} \geq \eta_r^\Delta$, where η_r^Δ is the singular value of the Laplace operator in the space $\mathbf{H}_{\neq 0}^1(Y_f)$ (with the same BCs, as in (3.11)). Obviously the orthogonality holds $\langle \mathbf{w}^r, \mathbf{w}^s \rangle_{Y_f} = \delta_{rs}$. We consider the spectral decomposition

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \hat{\alpha}_r \mathbf{w}^r, \quad c_0^2 \rho_1^1 \equiv p_1^1 = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \hat{\alpha}_r \pi^r. \quad (3.13)$$

so that (3.9) projected in the basis $\{(\mathbf{w}^s, \pi^s)\}_s$ can be written, as follows

$$\sum_r \left[\lambda \rho_0 \langle \mathbf{w}^r, \mathbf{w}^s \rangle_{Y_f} - \langle \pi^r, \nabla_y \cdot \mathbf{w}^s \rangle_{Y_f} + a_f(\mathbf{w}^r, \mathbf{w}^s) \right] \hat{\alpha}_r = - \langle 1, \mathbf{w}^s \rangle_{Y_f} \cdot \nabla_x p_1^0, \quad (3.14)$$

which yields

$$\hat{\alpha}_r = - \frac{1}{\rho_0(\lambda + \eta_r)} \boldsymbol{\beta}^r \cdot \nabla_x p_1^0, \quad \text{where } \boldsymbol{\beta}^r := \langle 1, \mathbf{w}^r \rangle_{Y_f}. \quad (3.15)$$

In the macroscopic mass balance arising from (3.6)₂, we shall need the effective seepage $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_1$ expressed using the average of $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0$ computed in Y_f , such that using (3.13) and (3.15),

$$\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_1 = \rho_0 \int_{Y_f} \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 = \rho_0 \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \hat{\alpha}_r \langle 1, \mathbf{w}^r \rangle_{Y_f} = -\rho_0 \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \frac{\boldsymbol{\beta}^r \otimes \boldsymbol{\beta}^r}{\rho_0(\lambda + \eta_r)} \cdot \nabla_x p_1^0 = -\tilde{\boldsymbol{\kappa}} \nabla_x p_1^0, \quad (3.16)$$

where the Darcy law is introduced in terms of the dynamic permeability,

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}(\lambda) = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \frac{\boldsymbol{\beta}^r \otimes \boldsymbol{\beta}^r}{\lambda + \eta_r} = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \tilde{\kappa}_r(\lambda) \mathbf{X}^r, \quad (3.17)$$

where $\tilde{\kappa}_r(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\lambda + \eta_r}$, and $\mathbf{X}^r = \boldsymbol{\beta}^r \otimes \boldsymbol{\beta}^r$.

Returning back into the time domain, $\mathbf{W}_1(t, x)$ is expressed using the time convolution involving the dynamic permeability $\mathcal{K}(t) = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \kappa_r(t) \mathbf{X}^r$, with $\kappa_r(t) = \exp\{-\eta_r t\}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{W}_1(t, \cdot) &= - \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{X}^r \int_0^t \exp\{-\eta_r(t - \tau)\} \nabla_x p_1^0(\tau, \cdot) d\tau \\ &= - \int_0^t \mathcal{K}(t - \tau) \nabla_x p_1^0(\tau, \cdot) d\tau . \end{aligned} \quad (3.18)$$

and

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0(t, x, y) = - \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{w}^r \rho_0^{-1} \boldsymbol{\beta}^r \cdot \int_0^t \exp\{-\eta_r(t - \tau)\} \nabla_x p_1^0(\tau, \cdot) d\tau . \quad (3.19)$$

3.2.2. Macroscopic AWP problem

The macroscopic problem in Ω is obtained by averaging (3.6)₂ in Y_f ,

$$\phi_f \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho_1^0 + \rho_0 \nabla_x \cdot \int_{Y_f} \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 = 0 , \quad (3.20)$$

where $\phi_f = |Y_f|/|Y|$. Furthermore, the density can be substituted due to the barotropic law, $\rho_1^0 = p_1^0/c_0^2$. The Laplace transformation can be applied, so that using the dynamic permeability defined in (3.17) the macroscopic mass balance (3.20) attains the following form

$$\lambda \frac{\phi_f}{c_0^2} \tilde{p}_1^0 - \nabla_x \cdot \tilde{\mathcal{K}}(\lambda) \nabla_x \tilde{p}_1^0 = 0 , \quad (3.21)$$

hence, in the time domain we get

$$\frac{\phi_f}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} p_1^0 - \nabla_x \cdot \int_0^t \mathcal{K}(t - \tau) \nabla_x p_1^0(\tau, \cdot) d\tau = 0 , \quad (3.22)$$

This presents the macroscopic model of the acoustic waves propagation in the homogenized porous structures. We recall that the two-scale velocity field $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0$ provides the driving force of the flow described in the 2nd order model.

3.3. Homogenization of the ASF problem

The 2nd order problem arising from (2.8) concerns the time-averaged fields describing the AS effect in the pores Ω_f^ε , so that, its the solutions $(\bar{\mathbf{v}}_2^\varepsilon, \bar{p}_2^\varepsilon, \bar{\rho}_2^\varepsilon)$ depend on ε . The following truncated expansions are considered (for the sake of simplicity, we drop the bar $(\bar{\quad})$ from the notation of the limit functions, although these present the time averages!)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_\varepsilon(\bar{\mathbf{v}}^\varepsilon(x, t)) &= \mathbf{v}_2^0(x, y, t) + \varepsilon \mathbf{v}_2^1(x, y, t) , \\ \mathcal{T}_\varepsilon(\bar{p}_2^\varepsilon(x, t)) &= p_2^0(x, t) + \varepsilon p_2^1(x, y, t) , \\ \mathcal{T}_\varepsilon(\bar{\rho}_2^\varepsilon(x, t)) &= \rho_2^0(x, t) + \varepsilon \rho_2^1(x, y, t) . \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

First we substitute (3.23) and also (3.3) in the continuity equation (2.8)₁ and collect the terms of orders $o(\varepsilon^{-1})$ and $o(\varepsilon^0)$; note that terms at $o(\varepsilon^1)$ which cannot be complete with the truncated expansions (3.23) are neglected in the 1st order homogenization, since they vanish in the limit $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. Therefore, in the unfolded domain $\Omega \times Y_f$ the continuity equation yields

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_y \cdot \mathbf{v}_2^0 &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho_2^0 + \rho_0 (\nabla_x \cdot \mathbf{v}_2^0 + \nabla_y \cdot \mathbf{v}_1^1) &= \nabla_y \cdot \overline{(\rho_1^0 \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0)}, \\ \rho_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v}_2^0 + \nabla_x p_2^0 + \nabla_y p_2^1 - \mu \nabla_y^2 \mathbf{v}_2^0 &= -\rho_0 \overline{(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 \cdot \nabla_y \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 + (\nabla_y \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0) \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0)}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.24)$$

where (3.24)₁ was applied in (3.24)₃. We introduce the weak form of the momentum equation (3.24)₃, since the projections using the inner products are employed in the spectral decomposition, as explained below. For any test function $\boldsymbol{\vartheta} \in C_0^\infty(\Omega; \mathbf{H}_{\neq 0}^1(Y_f))$, using the unfolding and integration by parts, we get (point-wise for a.a. $x \in \Omega$)

$$\begin{aligned} -\rho_0 \int_{Y_f} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v}_2^0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\vartheta} - \int_{Y_f} \bar{\mu} \nabla_y \mathbf{v}_2^0 : \nabla_y \boldsymbol{\vartheta} + \int_{Y_f} p_2^1 \nabla_y \cdot \boldsymbol{\vartheta} \\ = \int_{Y_f} \boldsymbol{\vartheta} \cdot \nabla_x p_2^0 + \rho_0 \int_{Y_f} \boldsymbol{\vartheta} \cdot \overline{(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 \cdot \nabla_y \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 + (\nabla_y \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0) \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0)}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.25)$$

recalling that \mathbf{v}_2^0, p_2^1 and p_2^0 represent the time averages of the second order (in α) functions, while $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0(x, y, t)$ is the two-scale in space time harmonic velocity.

Finally the barotropic approximation (2.8)₃ at orders $o(\varepsilon^0)$ and $o(\varepsilon^1)$ yields

$$\begin{aligned} p_2^0 &= c_0^2 \rho_2^0, \\ p_2^1 &= c_0^2 \rho_2^1 + c_0 c_0' (\rho_1^0)^2, \end{aligned} \quad (3.26)$$

respectively, which enable to express ρ_2^0 involved in (3.24). In fact, only (3.26)₁ is needed to obtain the macroscopic AS flow equation (ρ_2^1 is actually not needed, could be expressed using (3.26)₂). For this, (3.24)₂ is used only in the space-averaged form where the right hand side vanishes due to the Y -periodicity of $\rho_1^0 \mathbf{v}_1^0$.

3.3.1. Streaming source term for the ASF problem

The local AS flow described by the velocity \mathbf{v}_2^0 is governed by (3.25) involving the acoustic streaming source – the streaming force represented by the time-space average of the Reynolds stress expressed in terms of $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0$ given by (3.19) due to p_1^0 . To compute this streaming force, we derive the relationships which are valid for two wave types of waves, *i.e.* the standing waves in a bounded domain, and plane waves propagating in an unbounded domain, see Appendix B.2.

The real response $p_1^0(x, t)$ to an incident monochromatic wave with the angular frequency ω is expressed using the following general form in the form

$$p_1^0(x, t) = P(x) \cos \omega t - Q(x) \sin \omega t, \quad (3.27)$$

where P, Q are given in Appendix A.2 for the two above mentioned wave propagation types: (A.10) holds for the case of plane waves in infinite medium, such that P, Q can depend on \varkappa , while (A.6) provides P, Q in a bounded domain Ω for specific BCs on $\partial\Omega$.

Recalling (3.16)₁ and (3.18) which holds in the time domain, the velocity of the acoustic waves is expressed by

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0(t, x, y) = -\rho_0^{-1} \sum_r [\mathbf{w}^r(y) \boldsymbol{\beta}^r \cdot (\nabla_x P(x) \mathcal{J}_r(t) - \nabla_x Q(x) \mathcal{I}_r(t))] . \quad (3.28)$$

where $\mathcal{J}_r(t)$ and $\mathcal{I}_r(t)$ represent the convolutions of time harmonics (frequency ω) with the exponential attenuation, see (A.1), while $P(x)$ and $Q(x)$ are specific to the wave types, as explained above. Further we aim to rewrite (3.28) in a form suitable for homogenization of the 2nd order problem.

For this, we shall employ the following 2nd order tensors $\mathbf{G}^\otimes = (\mathbf{G}^{\alpha\beta}(x))$, with $\alpha, \beta = 1, 2$,

$$\mathbf{G}^{11} = \nabla P \otimes \nabla P , \quad \mathbf{G}^{12} = -\nabla P \otimes \nabla Q = (\mathbf{G}^{21})^T , \quad \mathbf{G}^{22} = \nabla Q \otimes \nabla Q , \quad (3.29)$$

and introduce time-dependent coefficients $\mathcal{M}_{rs}^\otimes = (\mathcal{M}_{rs}^{\alpha\beta}(t))$, such that for $\alpha, \beta = 1, 2$,

$$\mathcal{M}_{rs}^{11}(t) = \mathcal{J}_r(t) \mathcal{J}_s(t) , \quad \mathcal{M}_{rs}^{12}(t) = \mathcal{J}_r(t) \mathcal{I}_s(t) = \mathcal{M}_{sr}^{21}(t) , \quad \mathcal{M}_{rs}^{22}(t) = \mathcal{I}_r(t) \mathcal{I}_s(t) . \quad (3.30)$$

Now the streaming force in the right hand side of (3.25) can be evaluated. Let us define

$$\mathcal{S}(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0) = \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 \cdot \nabla_y \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 + (\nabla_y \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0) \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 = \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 \cdot \nabla_y \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 , \quad (3.31)$$

recalling $\nabla_y \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 = 0$. Upon substituting there from (3.28), due to (3.29)-(3.30)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0) &= \sum_r \sum_s \frac{1}{\rho_0^2} \mathbf{w}^s \cdot \nabla_y \mathbf{w}^r \beta_k^r \beta_l^s \sum_{\alpha, \beta=1,2} \mathcal{M}_{rs}^{\alpha\beta}(t) G_{kl}^{\alpha\beta} , \\ &= \sum_r \sum_s \mathbf{a}^{rs} \mathbf{Y}^{rs} : \mathbf{F}^{rs}(x, t) , \end{aligned} \quad (3.32)$$

where, recalling $\boldsymbol{\beta}^r = \langle 1, \mathbf{w}^r \rangle_{Y_f}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y}^{rs} &= \boldsymbol{\beta}^r \otimes \boldsymbol{\beta}^s , \\ \mathbf{a}^{rs}(y) &= (\rho_0)^{-2} \mathbf{w}^s \cdot \nabla_y \mathbf{w}^r \quad \text{defined for } y \in Y_f , \\ \mathbf{F}^{rs}(x, t) &= \sum_{\alpha, \beta=1,2} \mathbf{G}^{\alpha\beta}(x) \mathcal{M}_{rs}^{\alpha\beta}(t) . \end{aligned} \quad (3.33)$$

Further we shall neglect the evanescent parts of $\mathcal{I}_r(t)$ and $\mathcal{J}_r(t)$ associated with the transition effects, see (A.1). Hence, $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{\alpha\beta}(t)$ given by $\tilde{\mathcal{I}}_r(t)$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_r(t)$ only is required to express

the steady AS response, while disregarding the terms $\mathcal{I}_r(t) - \tilde{\mathcal{I}}_r(t)$ and $\mathcal{J}_r(t) - \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_r(t)$. Therefore, keeping the notation above introduced with $\tilde{\mathbf{F}}^{rs}$ modified by virtue of using $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{\alpha\beta}(t)$ in (3.33)₃, we can be rewrite (3.32), as follows

$$\tilde{\mathcal{S}}(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0)(t, \cdot) = \sum_r \sum_s \mathbf{a}^{rs}(y) \mathbf{Y}^{rs} : \tilde{\mathbf{F}}^{rs}(x, t). \quad (3.34)$$

Since the 2nd order problem describes the time averaged responses, by virtue of (3.34), the right hand side in (3.25) is expressed by $\overline{\mathcal{S}}^n(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0)(t, \cdot)$ involving the following integrals,

$$\overline{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{\alpha\beta n} = (nT)^{-1} \int_t^{t+nT} \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{\alpha\beta}(\tau) d\tau, \quad (3.35)$$

which are evaluated in Appendix A.1. It is worth to note that $\overline{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{\alpha\beta n}$ depends on the frequency of the harmonic (acoustic) response, but is constant in time, having neglected the transients effects. By the consequence, the time averaged of $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0)$ defined in (3.32) can be expressed using $\bar{\mathbf{F}}^{rs}(x)$ being constant in time,

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{\mathcal{S}}^n(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0)(t, x, y) &= (nT)^{-1} \int_t^{t+nT} \mathcal{S}(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0(\tau, \cdot)) d\tau \\ &= \mathcal{S}^*(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0) \equiv \sum_r \sum_s \mathbf{a}^{rs}(y) \mathbf{Y}^{rs} : \bar{\mathbf{F}}^{rs}(x), \end{aligned} \quad (3.36)$$

$$\text{where } \bar{\mathbf{F}}^{rs}(x, \omega) := \sum_{\alpha, \beta} \mathbf{G}(x)^{\alpha\beta} \overline{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{\alpha\beta n}.$$

Thus, $\overline{\mathcal{S}}^n = \mathcal{S}^*$ is constant in time, while neglecting initial conditions inducing the time-evanescent effects. In Remark 3, a simplified expression for computing $\bar{\mathbf{F}}^{rs}$ is given. When $\mathbf{G}^{12} = \mathbf{G}^{21}$, it holds that $\bar{\mathbf{F}}^{rs} = (\mathbf{G}^{11} + \mathbf{G}^{22}) \overline{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{11 n}$.

Remark 3. Due to (A.3), the tensor $\bar{\mathbf{F}}^{rs}(x, \omega)$ can be evaluated using the following simplified formula

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}}^{rs} = \sum_{\alpha, \beta} \mathbf{G}^{\alpha, \beta} \overline{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{\alpha, \beta n} = (\mathbf{G}^\circ \overline{\mathcal{M}}_{rs} + (\mathbf{G}^{12} - \mathbf{G}^{21}) \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{rs}), \quad (3.37)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{G}^\circ &= \mathbf{G}^{11} + \mathbf{G}^{22}, \\ \overline{\mathcal{M}}_{rs} &= \overline{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{11}, \quad \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{rs} = \overline{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{12}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.38)$$

Obviously, if $\mathbf{G}^{12} = \mathbf{G}^{21}$, the second term in (3.37) vanishes, hence $\sum_{\alpha, \beta} \mathbf{G}^{\alpha, \beta} \overline{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{\alpha, \beta n} = (\mathbf{G}^{11} + \mathbf{G}^{22}) \overline{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}$. This is the case of 1D problems treated in Appendix A.2; in particular, plane wave propagation is featured by $\nabla P \parallel \nabla Q$, i.e. $\mathbf{G}^{12} = \mathbf{G}^{21}$ holds.

3.3.2. Local responses expressed using the spectral decomposition

Although \mathcal{S}^* given in (3.36) is time independent, the use of the Laplace transformation is required due to the same reasons as in the case of the treatment of the 1st order problem, since $\nabla_x p_2^0$ may depend on time. Thus, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}\{\overline{\mathcal{S}(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0)}\}(\lambda) &= \mathcal{L}\{\overline{(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 \cdot \nabla_y \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 + (\nabla_y \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0) \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0)}\}(\lambda) = \mathcal{L}\{\overline{\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0 \cdot \nabla_y \hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0}\}(\lambda) \\ &= \frac{1}{\lambda} \mathcal{S}^*(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0) = -\frac{1}{\lambda} \sum_r \sum_s \mathbf{a}^{rs} \bar{\mathbf{F}}^{rs}(x, \omega) : \mathbf{Y}^{rs} . \end{aligned} \quad (3.39)$$

Note that λ (the Laplace transform variable) and ω (the acoustic wave frequency) are now considered as two independent variables in the 2nd order problem!

The couple $(\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_2^0, \tilde{p}_2^1)$ satisfies the microproblem arising from (3.24)₁ and (3.25), where the streaming source term is expressed using \mathcal{S}^* obtained in (3.39),

$$\begin{aligned} & -\lambda \rho_0 \int_{Y_f} \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_2^0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\vartheta} - \int_{Y_f} \bar{\mu} \nabla_y \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_2^0 : \nabla_y \boldsymbol{\vartheta} + \int_{Y_f} \tilde{p}_2^1 \nabla_y \cdot \boldsymbol{\vartheta} \\ &= \int_{Y_f} \boldsymbol{\vartheta} \cdot \nabla_x \tilde{p}_2^0 + \frac{\rho_0}{\lambda} \int_{Y_f} \boldsymbol{\vartheta} \cdot \mathcal{S}^*(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0) , \quad \forall \boldsymbol{\vartheta} \in \mathbf{H}_{\neq 0}^1(Y_f) , \\ & \int_{Y_f} q \nabla_y \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_2^0 = 0 , \quad \forall q^1 \in L^2(Y_f) . \end{aligned} \quad (3.40)$$

3.3.3. Spectral decomposition of the local AS flow fields

We proceed in analogy with the treatment of the 1st-order problem (3.9), since the problem (3.40) involves the same operator arising from the local Stokes flow problem. Therefore, the spectral decomposition of the local fields describing the AS flow are expressed in terms of the eigenvalues and eigenfunctions obtained in (3.11). Hence, in analogy with (3.13) involving coefficients $\hat{\alpha}_1^r$, coefficients α_2^r are now introduced in the decomposition of $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_2^0$ and \tilde{p}_2^1 ,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_2^0 = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \alpha_2^r \mathbf{w}^r , \quad \tilde{p}_2^1 = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \alpha_2^r \pi^r . \quad (3.41)$$

Upon substituting in (3.40) and testing there by $\mathbf{v} := \mathbf{w}^s$, which yields

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_r \left[\lambda \rho_0 \langle \mathbf{w}^r, \mathbf{w}^s \rangle_{Y_f} - \langle \pi^r, \nabla_y \cdot \mathbf{w}^s \rangle_{Y_f} + a_f(\mathbf{w}^r, \mathbf{w}^s) \right] \alpha^r &= - \langle 1, \mathbf{w}^s \rangle_{Y_f} \cdot \nabla_x \tilde{p}_2^0 \\ & \quad - \frac{\rho_0}{\lambda} \langle \mathcal{S}^*(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0), \mathbf{w}^s \rangle_{Y_f} , \end{aligned} \quad (3.42)$$

hence, coefficients α_2^r are computed, as follows (the notation introduced in (3.33) applies)

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \alpha_2^r &= -\frac{1}{\rho_0(\lambda + \eta_r)} \left(\boldsymbol{\beta}^r \cdot \nabla_x \tilde{p}_2^0 + \frac{\rho_0}{\lambda} \langle \mathcal{S}^*(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0), \mathbf{w}^r \rangle_{Y_f} \right) , \\ \alpha_2^r &= -\frac{1}{\rho_0(\lambda + \eta_r)} \left(\boldsymbol{\beta}^r \cdot \nabla_x \tilde{p}_2^0 + \frac{1}{\lambda} \sum_k \sum_l \mathcal{H}_{kl}^r \mathbf{Y}^{kl} : \bar{\mathbf{F}}^{kl}(x) \right) , \end{aligned} \quad (3.43)$$

where (3.39) has been used and the coefficients \mathcal{H}_{kl}^r are given, as follows

$$\mathcal{H}_{kl}^r = \rho_0 \langle \mathbf{a}^{kl}, \mathbf{w}^r \rangle_{Y_f} = \frac{1}{\rho_0} \int_{Y_f} (\mathbf{w}^l \cdot \nabla_y \mathbf{w}^k) \cdot \mathbf{w}^r. \quad (3.44)$$

Remark 4. The coefficients \mathcal{H}_{kl}^r are antisymmetric in the following sense: $\mathcal{H}_{kl}^r = -\mathcal{H}_{rl}^k$. Indeed, since $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{w}^l = 0$ and $\mathbf{w}^r \in \mathbf{H}_{\neq 0}^1(Y_f)$ for any $r = 1, 2, \dots$, the divergence theorem yields

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_0 \mathcal{H}_{kl}^r &= \int_{\partial Y_f} \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{w}^l (\mathbf{w}^k \cdot \mathbf{w}^r) - \int_{Y_f} \nabla_y \cdot \mathbf{w}^l (\mathbf{w}^k \cdot \mathbf{w}^r) - \int_{Y_f} (\mathbf{w}^l \cdot \nabla_y \mathbf{w}^r) \cdot \mathbf{w}^k \\ &= - \int_{Y_f} (\mathbf{w}^l \cdot \nabla_y \mathbf{w}^r) \cdot \mathbf{w}^k = -\rho_0 \mathcal{H}_{rl}^k. \end{aligned} \quad (3.45)$$

3.3.4. Macroscopic model of the ASF

The macroscopic flow is governed by the time averaged continuity equation (3.24)₂ which integrated over Y_f yields (note $c_0^2 \rho_2^0 = p_2^0$)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\phi_f}{c_0^2} \partial_t p_2^0 + \rho_0 \nabla_x \cdot \int_{Y_f} \mathbf{v}_2^0, \\ \lambda \frac{\phi_f}{c_0^2} p_2^0 + \nabla_x \cdot \mathbf{W}_2 = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (3.46)$$

where, in the second equation obtained by the Laplace-transformation in time, the mean velocity \mathbf{W}_2 is introduced using the spectral decomposition (3.41) and (3.43),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{W}_2(\lambda, x) &= \rho_0 \int_{Y_f} \mathbf{v}_2^0 \\ &= \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \beta^r \frac{1}{(\lambda + \eta_r)} \left(\beta^r \cdot \nabla_x p_2^0 + \frac{1}{\lambda} \sum_k \sum_l \mathcal{H}_{kl}^r \bar{\mathbf{F}}^{kl}(x, \omega) : \mathbf{Y}^{kl} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (3.47)$$

In the time domain, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{W}_2(t, x) &= \rho_0 \int_{Y_f} \mathbf{v}_2^0 = - \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \beta^r \otimes \beta^r \int_0^t \exp\{-\eta_r(t - \tau)\} \cdot \nabla_x p_2^0(\tau) d\tau \\ &\quad - \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \beta^r \frac{(1 - \exp\{-\eta_r t\})}{\eta_r} \sum_k \sum_l \mathcal{H}_{kl}^r \bar{\mathbf{F}}^{kl}(x, \omega) : \mathbf{Y}^{kl}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.48)$$

where the dynamic permeability $\mathcal{K}(t) = \sum_r \exp\{-\eta_r t\} \boldsymbol{\beta}^r \otimes \boldsymbol{\beta}^r$ defined in (3.17) and (3.18) can be identified and the AS seepage velocity \mathbf{w}^{AS} introduced, as follows

$$\mathbf{w}^{AS}(t, x) = \underline{\mathcal{A}}^\otimes(t) \odot \mathbf{G}^\otimes(x) := \sum_{\alpha, \beta} \underline{\mathcal{A}}^{\alpha\beta} : \mathbf{G}^{\alpha\beta} ,$$

$$\text{where } \underline{\mathcal{A}}^\otimes(t) = \sum_{r, k, l} \frac{(1 - \exp\{-\eta_r t\})}{\eta_r} \boldsymbol{\beta}^r \otimes (\boldsymbol{\beta}^k \otimes \boldsymbol{\beta}^l) \mathcal{H}_{kl}^r \overline{\mathcal{M}_{kl}^{\otimes n}} , \quad (3.49)$$

$$\text{thus } \mathcal{A}_{mij}^{\alpha, \beta}(t) = \sum_{r, k, l} \frac{(1 - \exp\{-\eta_r t\})}{\eta_r} \beta_m^r \otimes (\beta_i^k \otimes \beta_j^l) \mathcal{H}_{kl}^r \overline{\mathcal{M}_{kl}^{\alpha, \beta n}} .$$

The “ \odot ” operation concerns the summation over indices $i, j = 1, \dots, d$ and $\alpha, \beta = 1, 2$ involving 2nd order tensor $\mathbf{G}^\otimes = (G_{ij}^{\alpha\beta})$, see (3.36), and the 3rd order tensor $\underline{\mathcal{A}}^\otimes(t) = (\mathcal{A}_{mij}^{\alpha\beta}(t))$ which is fully determined by the microstructure properties and by ω involved through $\overline{\mathcal{M}_{kl}^{\alpha\beta n}}$. In the context of formula (3.49) and (A.3) revealing a kind of antisymmetry $\overline{\mathcal{M}_{rs}^{12n}} = -\overline{\mathcal{M}_{sr}^{12n}}$, it is worth to note that $\mathcal{H}_{kl}^r \neq \mathcal{H}_{lk}^r$, in general, hence the 2nd term in (3.37) will not disappear in the summation over mode indices r, s .

With this notation in hand, the macroscopic flow equation (3.46)₁ can be written, as follows,

$$\frac{\phi_f}{c_0^2} \partial_t p_2^0 - \nabla_x \cdot \int_0^t \mathcal{K}(t - \tau) \nabla_x p_2^0(\tau, \cdot) d\tau = \nabla_x \cdot \mathbf{w}^{AS} . \quad (3.50)$$

Steady state streaming. Consider p_2^0 is constant in time for any time $\tau > t_s$. Therefore, taking a sufficiently large $t \gg t_s$, the time convolution term can be approximated

$$\sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \int_0^t \exp\{-\eta_r(t - \tau)\} p_2^0(\tau) d\tau \approx \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\eta_r} p_2^0 . \quad (3.51)$$

In the steady state, the transition term $(1 - \exp\{-\eta_r t\}) \rightarrow 1$ with $t \rightarrow \infty$, so that $\underline{\mathcal{A}}^\otimes$ becomes stationary, but depends on the frequency ω through $\overline{\mathcal{M}_{kl}^{\otimes n}}$, see (3.29). By the consequence, the steady AS seepage velocity is obtained by the limit $\bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}(x) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{w}^{AS}(t, x)$,

$$\bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}(x, \omega) = \overline{\underline{\mathcal{A}}^\otimes} \odot \mathbf{G}^\otimes(x) ,$$

$$\overline{\underline{\mathcal{A}}^\otimes} = \sum_{r, k, l} \mathcal{H}_{kl}^r \overline{\mathcal{M}_{kl}^{\otimes n}} \frac{1}{\eta_r} \boldsymbol{\beta}^r \otimes \boldsymbol{\beta}^k \otimes \boldsymbol{\beta}^l . \quad (3.52)$$

Hence the steady state seepage velocity of the homogenized 2nd order problem is given by

$$\overline{\mathbf{W}}_2(x, \omega) = \mathbf{w}_2^P - \bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS} \text{ satisfying } \nabla_x \cdot \overline{\mathbf{W}}_2 = 0 ,$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{w}_2^P = - \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \frac{\boldsymbol{\beta}^r \otimes \boldsymbol{\beta}^r}{\eta_r} \cdot \nabla_x p_2^0 . \quad (3.53)$$

Note that \mathbf{w}_2^P is expressed by the Darcy law involving the “steady” permeability given by $\bar{\mathcal{K}} = \mathcal{K}(\lambda = 0)$, as defined in (3.17), while $\bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}$ describes the AS velocity due to the “acoustic forcing” introduced via \mathbf{S}^* . Upon substitution, we get the following elliptic PDE for p_2^0 ,

$$-\nabla_x \cdot (\bar{\mathcal{K}} \nabla_x p_2^0 + \bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}) = 0. \quad (3.54)$$

Remark 5. There are alternatives to present the macroscopic AS model (3.54). The AS “forcing” \mathbf{f}^{AS} can be introduced, such that

$$-\nabla_x \cdot [\bar{\mathcal{K}}(\nabla_x p_2^0 - \mathbf{f}^{AS})] = 0, \quad \text{with } \mathbf{f}^{AS} = -\bar{\mathcal{K}}^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}. \quad (3.55)$$

The example treated in Appendix B.2 shows the effect of AS “forcing” given by $\bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}$ due to the plane wave for the situation of impermeability condition at infinity, $\partial_\xi p_2(\xi = +\infty) = 0$, which produces the exponential increase of the AS pressure p_2 . The Helmholtz decomposition yields the scalar and vector potentials Φ^{AS} and Ψ^{AS}

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS} &= \nabla \Phi^{AS} + \nabla \times \Psi^{AS}, \\ \text{where } \nabla \times \nabla \times \Psi^{AS} &= \nabla \times \bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}, \\ \text{and } \nabla_x^2 \Phi^{AS} &= \nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.56)$$

The solenoidal part $\nabla \times \Psi^{AS}$ of the source $\bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}$ has no effect on the AS pressure, since (3.54) reads

$$-\nabla_x \cdot (\bar{\mathcal{K}} \nabla_x p_2^0) = \nabla_x^2 \Phi^{AS}. \quad (3.57)$$

In a case of isotropic tensor $\bar{\mathcal{K}} = K\mathbf{I}$, the AS induced pressure $p_2^0 = -\Phi^{AS}/K$ can be considered as the streaming source potential Φ^{AS} . Therefore, the streaming effects $\nabla_x p_2^0$ can be represented directly by $\bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}$ expressed in (3.49) using the acoustic response $\mathbf{G}^{\alpha\beta}$ computed in terms of $\nabla_x P$ and $\nabla_x Q$.

4. Numerical examples

We present the use of the homogenized model of the acoustic streaming (AS) in rigid porous media derived in this paper. To illustrate the AS effect at both the macroscopic and microscopic (pore) levels, we consider 2D microstructures which lead to a clear interpretation of the numerical simulations. Because of the topology restrictions (the solid cannot constitute a connected domain in 2D, see Fig. 1), the microstructures are formed by suspended (fixed) rigid particles surrounded by the fluid. Therefore, the solid particles represented by domain $Y_s \subset Y =]0, 1]^2$ in the periodic unit cell Y are referred to as the rigid “inclusions” in the fluid. To demonstrate the influence of the inclusion shape on the AS phenomenon observed at the two scales, two shapes are introduced – a “pastille”-shaped and a “droplet”-shaped ones, see Figs 3 and 5, parameterized by three parameters

to concern the relative size $|Y_s|/|Y|$, an aspect ratio (a dissimilarity to the circle) and the orientation angle - see Figs 3 and 5. The details are given below in Section 4.3.2.

We consider a fluid properties given by the air,

$$c_0 = 340 \text{ m/s}, \quad \mu = 1.8 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ Pa}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.2 \text{ kg/m}^3. \quad (4.1)$$

The scale parameter ε involved in the asymptotic analysis $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ is approximated by $\varepsilon_0 = 10^{-2}$ employed in all the examples reported below, recalling (3.1) which expresses the relationship between the pore size and the fluid rheology. Frequency $\omega = 10$ Hz is fixed in all the numerical studies, unless stated otherwise. In the context of the spectral decomposition, recalling (3.11), the 25 lowest eigenvalues η_r , $r = 1, \dots, 25$, are taken into account to establish the permeability and other quantities by virtue of (3.13) and (3.41) applied with the truncated summation with $r = 1, \dots, 25$. This approximation provides a sufficient accuracy verified by the comparison with the approach based on resolving the characteristic responses, see *e.g.* Rohan and Naili (2020).

4.1. Streaming in a porous layer – response to an inhomogeneous plane wave

We first consider a nonhomogeneous acoustic wave incident on a 2D porous layer. Accordingly the incident wave amplitude given by a L_2 -periodic function, the layer is represented by the macroscopic domain $\Omega =]0, L_1[\times]-L_2/2, +L_2/2[$, a rectangle with sides $L_1 = 1.5$ m and $L_2 = 1$ m. The boundary $\partial\Omega = \Gamma_I \cup \Gamma_O \cup \Gamma_- \cup \Gamma_+$ splits into four nonoverlapping parts, the rectangle edges $\Gamma_I = \{x \in \partial\Omega | x_1 = 0\}$, $\Gamma_O = \{x \in \partial\Omega | x_1 = L_2\}$,

Figure 2: Macroscopic domain Ω and unit reference cell Y .

Figure 4: The direction $\nu = (\cos \varphi, \sin \varphi)$ of the wave propagation in the porous medium with inclusions declined by angle θ from the lattice orientation.

Figure 3: Solid skeleton geometry: pastille-shaped and droplet-shaped inclusions orientation in the square periodic lattice.

Figure 5: Unit cell for various inclusion geometries: various elongation values e while $\phi_f = 0.861$ and $\theta = 0$. At $e = 0$ the inclusion is a disk.

and $\Gamma_{\pm} = \{x \in \partial\Omega | x_2 = \pm L_2/2\}$ see Fig.2. The incident wave with the frequency ω is specified by the amplitude $\hat{p}_1^0(x) = \hat{P} \sin\left(2\pi \frac{x_2}{L_2}\right)$ with a constant $\hat{P} \in \mathbb{R}$. The following boundary conditions are prescribed,

$$\begin{aligned} p_1^0 &= \hat{p}_1^0(x) \cos(\omega t) = \hat{P} \sin\left(2\pi \frac{x_2}{L_2}\right) \cos(\omega t) \quad \text{on } \Gamma_I, \\ p_1^0 &= 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_O, \\ p_1^0(x^-) &= p_1^0(x^+) \quad \text{at two homologous points } x^- \in \Gamma^-, \quad x^+ \in \Gamma^+, \end{aligned} \tag{4.2}$$

where $x^+ = x^- + (0, L_2)$, such that the solutions are L_2 -periodic in x_2 .

In Figs. 7 and 8, the macroscopic AS effect is reported using the macroscopic fields involved in the ASF homogenized model (3.54). The AWP problem was solved for the incident wave (4.2), yielding the acoustic field (A.6) expressed in terms of $P(x)$ and $Q(x)$, $x \in \Omega$, see Fig. 6. Using (3.29), tensor $\mathbf{G}^{\otimes}(x)$ is evaluated to compute the AS source $\bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}$ according to (3.52). For this, tensor $\bar{\mathbf{A}}^{\otimes}$ is calculated independently of the particular macroscopic problem, using the spectral decomposition (3.11)-(3.12) analyzed for the droplet particle. The results in Fig. 7 show the evanescence of the AS with the distance from Γ_I . Moreover, p_2^0 is $L_2/2$ -periodic, while the acoustic response p_1^0 is L_2 -periodic. Also the penetration depth of the AS is much narrower than that of the acoustic signal. Finally it is worth to note the difference between the AS source $\bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}$ and the seepage \mathbf{W}_2 velocities, see (3.53). Fig. 9 illustrates that AS at the micro-level varies with macroscopic location.

4.2. AS induced forces and moment acting on the inclusion

Besides the streaming velocity (seepage) \mathbf{W}_2 and the AS induced pressure p_2^0 observed at the macroscopic level, and the microscopic counterpart quantities \mathbf{v}_2^0 and p_2^1 it is of interest to evaluate forces and force-couples (moments) acting on the inclusion. For this, we need to reconstruct stress for the given finite scale approximation (recalling the use of $\varepsilon_0 = \ell/L = 0.01$), relating the microstructure size with fluid viscosity. The following two-scale approximations hold due to the expansions (assuming the steady state),

Figure 6: The macroscopic AWP in domain Ω – distributions of $P(x)$ and $Q(x)$, the real and the imaginary parts of the solution, respectively.

Figure 7: The macroscopic ASF in domain Ω – distribution of the streaming source $\bar{w}^{AS}(x)$ and effective velocity $\mathbf{W}_2(x)$ (colors correspond to magnitude intensity, while the direction is indicated by arrows).

Figure 8: The macroscopic ASF in domain Ω – distribution of pressure p_2^0 .

Figure 9: Local distribution of the velocity \mathbf{v}_2^0 and pressure p_2^1 at two macroscopic locations relative to the prescribed “cosine” (inhomogeneous) incident wave, see (4.2). Along the horizontal symmetry axis, *e.g* the position $x = (0.129, 0)^T$, the local AS distributions are symmetrical relative to the droplet shape symmetry.

$$\begin{aligned}
p_2^{\varepsilon_0}(x, y) &= p_2^0(x) + \varepsilon_0 \tilde{p}_2(x, y), \text{ with } \tilde{p}_2(x, y) = p_2^1(x, y) + (y - y^c) \cdot \nabla_x p_2^0(x), \\
\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{visc}(x, y) &= \bar{\mu} (\nabla_y \mathbf{v}_2^0 + (\nabla_y \mathbf{v}_2^0)^T), \\
\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}(x, y) &= \tilde{p}_2(x, y) \mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{visc}(x, y), \\
\text{hence } \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{AS, \varepsilon_0} &= p_2^{\varepsilon_0} \mathbf{I} + \varepsilon_0 \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{visc} = p_2^0 \mathbf{I} + \varepsilon_0 \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}},
\end{aligned} \tag{4.3}$$

where $y^c \in Y$ denotes the barycenter of Y , *i.e.* $y^c = \int_Y y$. For the particular microstructure with one inclusion Y_s , periodic cell Y can be defined to merge its barycenter with the one of inclusion Y_s . Note that only the spherical stress p_2^0 is of order $o(1)$ in ε , whereas stress of order $o(\varepsilon)$ represented by $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$, besides the viscous stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{visc}$, involves also the effect of the macroscopic pressure gradient, $\nabla_x p_2^0$.

The AS generate stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{AS, \varepsilon_0}$ which in the form of traction $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{AS, \varepsilon_0} \cdot \mathbf{n}$ acts on surface of the solid inclusions; the total force \vec{F}^ε transmitted to the porous solid converges, as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
\vec{F}^\varepsilon &= \int_{\Gamma_{fs}^\varepsilon} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{AS, \varepsilon} \cdot \mathbf{n} d\Gamma = \int_\Omega \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \int_\Gamma (p_2^0(x) + \varepsilon \tilde{p}_2(x, y) + \varepsilon \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{visc}(x, y)) \cdot \mathbf{n} d\Gamma_y dx \\
&\rightarrow \int_\Omega \int_\Gamma (\tilde{p}_2 + \bar{\mu} (\nabla_y \mathbf{v}_2^0 + (\nabla_y \mathbf{v}_2^0)^T)) d\Gamma_y dx = \int_\Omega \vec{f}^\delta(x) dx,
\end{aligned} \tag{4.4}$$

where $\vec{f}^\delta(x)$ is the local force density computed using the traction of the stress on the single inclusion at $x \in \Omega$. In analogy, moment \vec{m}^δ of the traction stress relative to the cell centers y^c can be established, so that for $x \in \Omega$ with a given $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}(x, \cdot)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\vec{f}^\delta(x) &= \int_\Gamma \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \mathbf{n} d\Gamma_y, \\
\vec{m}^\delta(x) &= \int_\Gamma (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \times (y - y^c) d\Gamma_y.
\end{aligned} \tag{4.5}$$

It is worth noting that the force couples (moments) defined relative to the local positions y^c presents an effect of order $o(\varepsilon)$. There are 3 contributions in the force definition:

$\vec{f}^\delta = \vec{f}_\mu + \vec{f}_p + \vec{f}_g$, where

$$\begin{aligned}
\vec{f}_\mu &= \int_\Gamma \bar{\mu} (\nabla_y \mathbf{v}_2^0 + (\nabla_y \mathbf{v}_2^0)^T) \cdot \mathbf{n} dS_y, \\
\vec{f}_p &= - \int_\Gamma p_2^1 \mathbf{n} dS_y, \\
\vec{f}_g &= - \int_\Gamma (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^c) \cdot \nabla_x p_2^0 \mathbf{n} dS_y.
\end{aligned} \tag{4.6}$$

Also moment $\vec{m}^\delta = \vec{m}_\mu + \vec{m}_p + \vec{m}_g$ can be expressed using 3 contributions define in analogy with (4.6).

4.3. Streaming due to waves propagating in infinite media

In order to explore the influence of the microstructure on the AS, we consider a plane acoustic wave, as defined in (A.7) for which technical details associated with the AS source are presented in Appendix A.2 and Appendix B.2. Recall that $\xi = \boldsymbol{\nu} \cdot \mathbf{x}$ determines the position in the wave direction, see (A.7), whereby the boundary conditions on p_2^0 are: $p_2^0(\xi = 0) = 0$ and $\partial_\xi p_2^0(\xi = +\infty) = 0$.

Obviously, the response of both the AWP and ASF problems describing the acoustic waves and the AS response depend on the microstructure which is described by the particles shapes and their mutual position within the periodic lattice. In this respect, we consider the two types of the particles, being shaped as droplets, or pastilles featured by one, or two axes symmetry, respectively; the (non)symmetry is one of the most important factors affecting the AS response. The study reported below concerns the following phenomena:

- Frequency ω of the incident acoustic waves;
- Particle shape and relative size; the two particle types represented by domain $Y_s \subset Y$, and the fluid volume fraction $\phi_f = 1 - |Y_s|/|Y|$.
- Orientation of the particles relative to the lattice orientation and the direction of the wave propagation; the waves propagating in direction $\boldsymbol{\nu} = (\cos \varphi, \sin \varphi)$, the particle symmetry axis is declined by angle θ relative to the lattice orientation alligned with x_1 axis, see Fig. 4. Note that square lattice admits two symmetry systems of orthogonal axes defined by $\varphi = 0$ and $\varphi = \pi/4$.

It is important to note that the streaming source can be expressed by the 'aligned' and 'transverse' component with respect to the wave propagation direction, $\bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS} = (w_\nu^{AS}, w_\perp^{AS})$. In analogy, also the components f_ν° and f_\perp° of the force \vec{f}° acting on the inclusions are distinguished.

4.3.1. Influence of the frequency

First, we consider waves propagating along the "horizontal" direction, i.e. $\varphi = 0$, see Fig.4. By the symmetry arguments, since the particles are aligned with the lattice and the wave direction, such that $\theta = \varphi = 0$, the macroscopic problem is unidirectional (describing a 1D continuum), whereby $\bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS} = w_\nu^{AS} \boldsymbol{\nu}$, $\vec{f}^\circ = f^\circ \boldsymbol{\nu}$, and the moment vanishes $\vec{m}^\circ = 0$, see (4.5). Hence, in (4.6), the "perpendicular" components of the force vanish, $\vec{f}^\circ \cdot \boldsymbol{\nu}^\perp = 0$, where $\boldsymbol{\nu}^\perp \cdot \boldsymbol{\nu} = 0$. Obviously, the distribution of microscopic streaming in Y_f is two-dimensional, see Fig.14.

The frequency influence is explored in a large frequency band $10^{-3}\text{Hz} \leq \omega \leq 10^5\text{Hz}$. Fig.10 shows a significant sensitivity of the dynamic permeability $K_\nu(\omega)$ in the frequency range $\omega \in [1, 100]$, whereas almost no influence seen outside of this range. Moreover, the permeability vanishes for larger values of ω . The number of eigenvalues taken into account is 25, see Fig.11, which provides a good approximation.

Figure 10: The variation of permeability $K_\nu(\omega)$ with frequency ω , (for $\nu = (1, 0)^T$, *i.e.* $\varphi = 0$, and $\theta = 0$), the semi-log plot is employed. The dispersion is remarkable in the frequency range $\omega \in [0, 100]$ Hz which is considered in Figs. 12 and 13. Red solid line: modulus, blue dashed line: real part, green dotted line: imaginary part (a different scale is used for the imaginary part than for the real part and modulus).

Figure 11: The steady permeability magnitudes $|\bar{K}_\nu|$ depending on the number of considered eigenvalues.

Figure 12: Distribution of pressure $p_2^0(\xi)$ and streaming source $w_\nu^{AS}(\xi)$ along the wave direction, for selected values of frequency ω .

Figure 13: Macroscopic AS effects depending on frequency $\omega \in [0, 100]$ Hz. Left: pressure $p_2^0(\omega)|_{\xi=+\infty}$ (blue) and streaming source $w_\nu^{AS}(\omega)|_{\xi=0}$ (red). Right: components of the AS induced force acting on particles at $\xi = 0$, dependence on ω ; force decomposition according to (4.6).

The AS effect at the macroscopic level is illustrated in Fig. 12, where the spatial distribution of the induced pressure p_2^0 and the AS source velocity w_ν^{AS} are displayed, as computed due to (B.14) involving the acoustic response tensor \mathbf{G}° given by (3.29). Note that $w_2^P(\xi) = w_\nu^{AS}(\xi) = -\bar{\mathcal{K}}_{\nu\nu}\partial_\xi p_2^0$, hence $W_2 = w_2^P - w_\nu^{AS} = 0$, *i.e.* the total macroscopic seepage induced by the AS vanishes. So, the macroscopic effect of the AS is the induced pressure and also the force, as illustrated in Fig. 13; the contributions due to the pressure gradient $\partial_\xi p_2^0$ and the viscous stress are much less important than the local pressure nonuniformity $p_2^1(y)$, $y \in \Gamma$. No moment is induced by the AS, *i.e.* $m^\circ = 0$, since $\varphi = \theta = 0$.

4.3.2. Influence of shape, volume fraction, and directionality

We now illustrate how the AS effect depends on the shape and the relative size of the inclusions. We only consider two families of shapes to investigate the aspect of the symmetry: the droplet-shaped shapes with 1 axis of symmetry only, and the pastille-shaped shapes with 2 axes of symmetry, as shown in Fig.3. Both these families are generated by varying an elongation parameter e related to two geometric parameters r and h explained in Fig.5. For the pastille-shaped inclusion $e = (h/r)/(h/r)^{\max}$, whereas $e = \tan^{-1}(h/r)/\tan^{-1}(h/r)^{\max}$ for the droplet-shaped inclusion; parameter $(h/r)^{\max}$ is the maximum allowed ratio h/r . Clearly, for $h = 0$, also $e = 0$ by the two definitions, so that the inclusion is a circle of the radius r is the reference shape for the two families. Other two parameters of interest, describing the microstructure of the porous periodic medium, are the fluid volume fraction ϕ_f , and the symmetry axis orientation θ , see Fig.3.

In the previous sections 4.1 and 4.3.1, all the results are computed for the droplet-shaped inclusion characterized by $\phi_f = 0.861$, $\theta = 0$ and $\tan^{-1}(h/r) = 5\pi/16$ which is from now on associated with the maximal elongation value $e = 100\%$.

First we consider the shape and size variation for the droplet inclusions aligned with the wave propagation *i.e.* $\theta = \varphi = 0$, the response is displayed for the macroscopic positions $\xi = 0$ and $\xi = +\infty$ where maximum values of w_ν^{AS} and p_2^0 are attained, respectively. Fig. 14(left) shows that macroscopic velocity w_ν^{AS} increases in response to increasing the particle non-symmetry (the “eccentricity” of the shape relatively to the barycenter). No AS effect appears for the perfectly symmetric shape of the circular inclusion, $e = 0$, so both p_2^0 and w_ν^{AS} vanish, although the local AS is observed. For the pastille-shaped inclusion featured by the two symmetry axes, no macroscopic AS appears, *i.e.* $w_\nu^{AS} = 0$ for any e , although the local AS is observed, see also Fig.18. Regarding the droplet-shaped inclusion, Fig. 14(right) shows local extreme values of p_2^0 and w_ν^{AS} for the size $\phi_f \approx 90\%$, this might be a challenge for optimization of the packing density concerning the induced AS effect.

Series of Figs. 15,16 and 17 illustrate the AS effect dependence on the particle alignment with the lattice orientation, angle θ , and with the wave direction, angle φ , see Fig. 4. The following cases are explored: $\varphi \in [-\pi, +\pi]$, while $\theta = 0$, Fig. 15; fixed $\varphi = 0$, while varying $\theta \in [-\pi, +\pi]$, Fig. 16; synchronous variation of both angles $\varphi = \theta$, so the axis of the particle symmetry is aligned with the wave direction, Fig. 17 (left); an analogous study: synchronous variation of both angles, but $\varphi - \theta = \pi/2$, Fig. 17 (right).

Obviously, the transverse components w_\perp^{AS} and f_\perp° may not vanish at the same time as the aligned components w_ν^{AS} and f_ν° . The numerical results confirm the importance of

the structure symmetry axis and orientation with respect to the wave propagation. The following conjectures can be stated for the droplet shaped particles (1 axis of symmetry in 2D, the proofs are beyond the scope of this paper).

- If $\phi - \theta = 0$, whereas $\theta \in \{0, \pi/2, \pi/4\}$, *i.e.* the wave propagation is *colinear* with the particle symmetry axis being aligned with a symmetry axis of the lattice, then $w_{\perp}^{AS} = 0$, $f_{\perp}^{\circ} = 0$ and $m^{\circ} = 0$, see Fig. 17(left).
- If $\phi - \theta = \pi/2$, whereas $\theta \in \{0, \pi/2, \pi/4\}$, *i.e.* the wave propagation is *perpendicular* to the the symmetry axis of the particle which is aligned a symmetry axis of the lattice, then $w_{\nu}^{AS} = 0$, $f_{\nu}^{\circ} = 0$ and $m^{\circ} = 0$, see Fig. 17(right).

Fig. 16 also reveals that the longitudinal AS macroscopic velocity w_{ν} is correlated with the longitudinal force f_{ν} when rotating the particle orientation relative to the wave direction $\boldsymbol{\nu}$. The transverse force component f_{\perp} is maximized (whereby the longitudinal component f_{ν} is minimized) when this axis is orthogonal to $\boldsymbol{\nu}$, as can be seen in Fig. 17; in analogy, it holds also for the AS macroscopic velocity w_{\perp} .

The moment m° does not vanish, in general, as illustrated in Figs. 15 and 16. For instance, $m^{\circ} \neq 0$ if the symmetry axis of the particle is not aligned with the lattice, $\theta \notin \{0, \pi/2\}$, even if the wave propagation is colinear with the lattice axes, $\varphi = 0$, see Fig. 16.

The local distribution of the AS effect at micro-level is plotted in Fig. 18 for fixed $\varphi = 0$, while varying $\theta \in [0, \pi/2]$. We observe that the distribution is symmetric for the pastille-shaped inclusion, making vanishing the macroscopic AS, while the AS local field is symmetric only when $\theta = 0$ or $\theta = \pi/2$ for the droplet-shaped inclusion.

Figure 14: Influence of the microstructure on the AS – shape morphing and size of droplet inclusion, for $\theta = \varphi = 0$. Left: influence of the elongation e (fixed size $\phi_f = 86\%$). Right: influence of the relative size of the inclusion represented by the porosity ϕ_f (fixed shape elongation $e = 100\%$). Top: macroscopic streaming effect: Dependence of the streaming source $w_{\nu}^{AS}|_{\xi=0}$ (red) and AS induced pressure $p_2^0(\xi = +\infty)$ (blue) on e and ϕ_f . Bottom: microscopic streaming effect: Local distribution of the velocity $\mathbf{v}_2^0(\xi = 0)$ and pressure $p_2^1(\xi = +\infty)$ in Y_f .

Figure 15: Top and middle: The longitudinal (red solid line) and normal (blue dashed line) projection of the streaming source $\bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}|_{\xi=0}$ and AS induced force $\bar{f}^0|_{\xi=0}$ in dependence of the wave propagation direction $\varphi \in [-\pi, +\pi]$ (fixed inclusion orientation $\theta = 0$). Bottom: moment m° variation with φ ; contributions m_μ, m_p, m_g according to (4.6).

Figure 16: Top and middle: The longitudinal (red solid line) and normal (blue dashed line) projection of the streaming source $\bar{w}^{AS}|_{\xi=0}$ and AS induced force $\vec{f}^o|_{\xi=0}$ in dependence of the inclusion angle orientation $\theta \in [-\pi, +\pi]$ (fixed wave direction $\varphi = 0$). Bottom: moment m^o variation with θ ; contributions m_μ, m_p, m_g according to (4.6).

Figure 17: The projections of the streaming source \bar{w}^{AS} and AS induced force \vec{f}^o and moment m^o contributions in dependence of θ and φ with $\theta = \varphi$ (left) and $\theta \perp \varphi$ (right). Evaluated at position $\xi = 0$.

Figure 18: Local distribution of the velocity magnitude $|v_2^0$ and pressure p_2^1 in Y_f for various orientations of the pastille-shaped or droplet-shaped inclusion, while $\varphi = 0$. Evaluated at position $\xi = 0$.

Figure 19: The dependence of moment m^o on the elongation parameter e , when the inclusion symmetry axis are declined by $\theta = \pi/4$ (while $\varphi = 0$). Blue: droplet-shaped particle. Red; pastille-shaped particle.

The moment m° acting on the droplet and pastille shaped inclusions depends qualitatively on both the angles φ and θ . In addition to the observations stated above, Fig. 19 reveals the effect of shapes morphing due to the variation of e ; a significant difference between the moments m° generated for the two shapes appears.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we considered the acoustic streaming (AS) as the secondary effects of the acoustic waves in Newtonian fluids saturating rigid porous skeletons with periodic microstructures. The objective of this study was to derive a model describing the AS phenomenon in the homogenized porous medium and to study how the AS depends on selected parameters of the microstructure.

The modelling approach is based on the slow streaming approximation using the perturbation analysis Nyborg (1953); Lighthill (1978) which leads to splitting the nonlinear problem governed by the Navier Stokes equations into two linear subproblems: the acoustic wave propagation (AWP) provides the AS source (“acoustic forcing”) for the AS flow (ASF) problem. The asymptotic method of homogenization is employed to derive effective models for both AWP and ASF problems. For AWP, the standard non-stationary “Darcy flow” model is obtained, involving the dynamic permeability which, in our study, is expressed using the spectral decomposition of the Stokes flow problem in the representative pore. This spectral decomposition is used also in the homogenized ASF model which involves the same dynamic permeability as the one in the AWP model, although the steady AS is described in terms of the static permeability associated with this dynamic one. The macroscopic ASF attains the same form as the one governing the AWP, however, with the right hand side source which is the “acoustic forcing” expressed in terms of AS source velocity. This modelling issue is summarized in Remark 5.

The model has been implemented using the finite element method to obtain numerical solutions to the both AWP and ASF problems. Although the theoretical result is derived for the 3D porous structures, the AS phenomenon was presented using 2D examples where the solid phase is disconnected, being referred to as inclusions or particles. The reported numerical simulations show how the microstructure influences the AS flow and generated forces acting on the solid scaffolds – here represented by the solid inclusions. Although, in general, the AS response depends on the particular case characterized by the scaffold geometry, fluid properties (results presented for air only) and applied frequency, general observations can be summarized, as follows; we adhere to the notation used in Section 4. a) Any particle shape induces the local AS (micro-AS). b) The global (macroscopic) effects may vanish namely if the microstructure geometry is symmetric with respect to the periodic lattice orientation and propagation direction of the acoustic wave (e.g. the rond particle or pastille-shaped wile $\varphi = 0$). c) In general, increasing the particle non-symmetry (the “shape eccentricity” in the sense of the boundary moment relatively to the barycenter) also the AS macroscopic velocity is increased.

Since the solid skeleton is rigid, only the pressure waves propagate. Therefore, the acoustic response and hence also the AS vanish with increasing frequency, noting that

the “solid particles” (representing any solid skeleton in our 2D setting) are considered as fixed. To explore the ultrasound range of frequencies Raghavan (2018); Price et al. (2023); Wang et al. (2023), the solid elasticity would have to be considered, *i.e.* particles treated as vibrating in the fluid. Nevertheless, this study contributes to the future homogenization-based modelling of the AS in fluid suspensions constituted by rigid or deformable particles, including particulate flows in periodic deformable scaffolds. By the consequence, the AS can lead to perturbation of the microstructure due to the deformation or particle motion, which, in principle, introduces the modulation effect of the acoustic response and, hence, of the AS. In this context, the present study is the first step showing a rigorous and computationally tractable modelling approach which will be developed further to comprise elastic solid phase and moving rigid, or deformable particles. Therefore, the results of this paper can stimulate the research in tissue biomedicine, engineering and chemistry.

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Appendix A. Harmonic response of the 1st order problem – acoustic waves

Appendix A.1. Time harmonic responses

Some auxiliary calculations are needed to express the streaming term $\mathcal{S}(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1^0)$ involved in the 2nd order problem. Namely the formula (3.36) for the time-averaged AS source term is shown. Due to (3.27), the following convolution integrals are involved in the definition $\mathcal{M}_{rs}^{\alpha\beta}$, $\alpha, \beta = 1, 2$, see (3.30),

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{J}_r(t) &= \int_0^t e^{-\eta_r(t-\tau)} \cos \omega \tau d\tau = \frac{1}{\omega^2 + \eta_r^2} (\eta_r \cos \omega t + \omega \sin \omega t - \eta_r e^{-\eta_r t}) \\ &= \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_r(t) + \frac{\omega}{\omega^2 + \eta_r^2} e^{-\eta_r t}, \\ \mathcal{I}_r(t) &= \int_0^t e^{-\eta_r(t-\tau)} \sin \omega \tau d\tau = \frac{1}{\omega^2 + \eta_r^2} (\eta_r \sin \omega t - \omega \cos \omega t + \omega e^{-\eta_r t}) \\ &= \tilde{\mathcal{I}}_r(t) + \frac{\omega}{\omega^2 + \eta_r^2} e^{-\eta_r t},\end{aligned}\tag{A.1}$$

where the evanescent parts $\mathcal{I}_r(t) - \tilde{\mathcal{I}}_r(t)$ and $\mathcal{J}_r(t) - \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_r(t)$ associated with the transition effects are neglected. Hence, only the time-period mean of the parts $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{\alpha\beta}(\tau)$ given by $\tilde{\mathcal{I}}_r(t)$

and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_r(t)$ will be used:

$$\begin{aligned}
\overline{\mathcal{M}_{rs}^{11}}^n &= (nT)^{-1} \int_t^{t+nT} \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{11}(\tau) d\tau \\
&= (nT)^{-1} \int_t^{t+nT} \frac{\eta_r \eta_s \cos^2 \omega \tau + (\eta_r \omega + \eta_s \omega) \sin \omega \tau \cos \omega \tau + \omega^2 \sin^2 \omega \tau}{(\omega^2 + \eta_r^2)(\omega^2 + \eta_s^2)} d\tau \\
&= \frac{\eta_r \eta_s + \omega^2}{2(\omega^2 + \eta_r^2)(\omega^2 + \eta_s^2)}, \\
\overline{\mathcal{M}_{rs}^{22}}^n &= (nT)^{-1} \int_t^{t+nT} \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{rs}^{11}(\tau) d\tau \\
&= (nT)^{-1} \int_t^{t+nT} \frac{\eta_r \eta_s \sin^2 \omega \tau - (\eta_r \omega + \eta_s \omega) \sin \omega \tau \cos \omega \tau + \omega^2 \cos^2 \omega \tau}{(\omega^2 + \eta_r^2)(\omega^2 + \eta_s^2)} d\tau \\
&= \frac{\eta_r \eta_s + \omega^2}{2(\omega^2 + \eta_r^2)(\omega^2 + \eta_s^2)}, \\
\overline{\mathcal{M}_{rs}^{12}}^n &= (nT)^{-1} \int_t^{t+nT} \frac{(\eta_r \eta_s - \omega^2)(1/2) \sin 2\omega \tau - \eta_r \omega \cos^2 \omega \tau + \omega \eta_s \sin^2 \omega \tau}{(\omega^2 + \eta_r^2)(\omega^2 + \eta_s^2)} d\tau \\
&= \frac{(\eta_s - \eta_r)\omega}{2(\omega^2 + \eta_r^2)(\omega^2 + \eta_s^2)}.
\end{aligned} \tag{A.2}$$

Consequently, $\overline{\mathcal{M}_{rs}^{\alpha\beta}}^n$ are constant, but depend on frequency ω of incident (plane) waves. Therefore, tensors $\mathbf{F}^{rs}(x, \omega)$ introduced in (3.36) are constant in time. It is easy to see that

$$\overline{\mathcal{M}_{rs}^{12}}^n = -\overline{\mathcal{M}_{sr}^{12}}^n, \text{ and } \overline{\mathcal{M}_{rs}^{11}}^n = \overline{\mathcal{M}_{sr}^{22}}^n \tag{A.3}$$

recalling that $\overline{\mathcal{M}_{rs}^{12}}^n = \overline{\mathcal{M}_{sr}^{21}}^n$ by definition.

Appendix A.2. Acoustic waves in waveguides and infinite media

To evaluate the streaming source \mathbf{S} , acoustic wave response in the form (3.27) must be computed in terms of $P(x)$ and $Q(x)$, hence $\mathbf{G}(x)$ defined in (3.29) and involved in (3.49) can be evaluated.

Bounded porous waveguides. In a bounded domain Ω representing a waveguide occupied by the homogenized structure, the harmonic stationary wave characterized by the frequency ω and the complex amplitude is given in the form

$$\tilde{p}_1^0(t, x) = p_1^0 \exp\{i\omega t\}. \tag{A.4}$$

Substituting in (3.22), see (3.18), yields the following integral

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_0^t \exp\{-\eta_r(t - \tau)\} \exp\{i\omega \tau\} d\tau &= \exp\{-\eta_r t\} \int_0^t \exp\{(i\omega - \eta_r)\tau\} d\tau \\
&= \frac{\exp\{i\omega\} - \exp\{-\eta_r t\}}{i\omega + \eta_r} \approx \frac{\exp\{i\omega\}}{i\omega + \eta_r}.
\end{aligned} \tag{A.5}$$

where the steady state approximation holds for all $t > t_s$ with $t_s > 0$ sufficiently large, noting that $\eta_r > 0$ for all modes $r = 1, 2, \dots$. Hence, we get a boundary value problem for the complex amplitudes p_1^0 satisfying (3.21) where $\lambda := i\omega$, being imposed in Ω with suitable boundary conditions describing an incident wave on a portion of the waveguide boundary, see Remark 1. The real steady oscillatory response is given by

$$\Re \tilde{p}_1^0 = P(x) \cos \omega t - Q(x) \sin \omega t, \quad \text{where} \quad P(x) = \Re p_1^0, \quad Q(x) = \Im p_1^0. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Infinite porous medium. As an alternative, we can consider acoustic waves propagating in an infinite domain occupied by the homogenized porous medium. Then the homogeneous plane wave is expressed in the form (note $\lambda := i\omega$, the complex wave amplitude denoted by p_1^0 is now a constant),

$$p_1^0 = \hat{p}_1^0 \exp\{-i\boldsymbol{\kappa} \boldsymbol{\nu} \cdot \mathbf{x}\}, \quad \hat{p}_1^0 \in \mathbb{R}, \quad \xi = \boldsymbol{\nu} \cdot \mathbf{x}, \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where co-ordinate ξ is introduced with respect to the propagation direction vector $\boldsymbol{\nu}$, $|\boldsymbol{\nu}| = 1$. Upon substituting in (3.21), the following dispersion equation for the wave number $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ is obtained,

$$\boldsymbol{\kappa}^2 = -i\omega \frac{\phi_f \rho_0}{c_0^2} \left(\sum_r \frac{X_\nu^r}{\eta_r + i\omega} \right)^{-1}, \quad \text{where } X_\nu^r = \mathbf{X}^r : \boldsymbol{\nu} \otimes \boldsymbol{\nu}. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Confining to the real part of the plane wave with a real amplitude of the incident wave $\hat{p}_1^0 \in \mathbb{R}$, (A.7) yields

$$\Re \tilde{p}_1^0 = \tilde{p}_1^\boldsymbol{\kappa} = P(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \xi) \cos \omega t - Q(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \xi) \sin \omega t, \quad (\text{A.9})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} P(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \xi) &= \hat{p}_1^0 \cos \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \xi \exp\{\boldsymbol{\kappa}_I \xi\}, \\ Q(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \xi) &= \hat{p}_1^0 \sin \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \xi \exp\{\boldsymbol{\kappa}_I \xi\}, \\ \nabla P(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \xi) &= \boldsymbol{\nu} \hat{p}_1^0 g_P, \quad g_P = (\boldsymbol{\kappa}_I \cos \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \xi - \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \sin \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \xi) \exp\{\boldsymbol{\kappa}_I \xi\}, \\ \nabla Q(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \xi) &= -\boldsymbol{\nu} \hat{p}_1^0 g_Q, \quad g_Q = (\boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \cos \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \xi + \boldsymbol{\kappa}_I \sin \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \xi) \exp\{\boldsymbol{\kappa}_I \xi\}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Recalling (3.37) and (3.38), $\mathbf{G}^\circ = \nabla P \otimes \nabla P + \nabla Q \otimes \nabla Q = \boldsymbol{\nu} \otimes \boldsymbol{\nu} (g_P^2 + g_Q^2)$, straightforward calculations lead to

$$\begin{aligned} g_P^2 &= (\hat{p}_1^0)^2 \exp\{2\boldsymbol{\kappa}_I \xi\} (\boldsymbol{\kappa}_R^2 \sin^2 \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \xi + \boldsymbol{\kappa}_I^2 \cos^2 \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \xi - \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \boldsymbol{\kappa}_I \sin 2\boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \xi), \\ g_Q^2 &= (\hat{p}_1^0)^2 \exp\{2\boldsymbol{\kappa}_I \xi\} (\boldsymbol{\kappa}_I^2 \sin^2 \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \xi + \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R^2 \cos^2 \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \xi + \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \boldsymbol{\kappa}_I \sin 2\boldsymbol{\kappa}_R \xi), \\ \mathbf{G}^\circ(\xi) &= \boldsymbol{\nu} \otimes \boldsymbol{\nu} (g_P^2 + g_Q^2) = (\hat{p}_1^0)^2 \exp\{2\boldsymbol{\kappa}_I \xi\} |\boldsymbol{\kappa}|^2 \boldsymbol{\nu} \otimes \boldsymbol{\nu}, \quad |\boldsymbol{\kappa}|^2 = \boldsymbol{\kappa}_R^2 + \boldsymbol{\kappa}_I^2. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

This result is employed below in Appendix B.2 devoted to the plane wave propagation featured by $\nabla P \parallel \nabla Q$.

Appendix B. 1D problem of the AS in homogenized porous structures

To illustrate the two-scale modelling of the AS in periodic rigid scaffolds, we consider situations when the macroscopic problem response depends on one macroscopic variable. This may happen naturally in a case of infinite media with respect to two spatial coordinates x_i , $i = 2, 3$ leading to a problem imposed in a layer with x_1 being the transverse coordinate, or in the case of the halfspace spanned by $x_1 > 0$. By virtue of the harmonic wave propagation, we employ the Fourier transformation: $\mathcal{F}\{f(t)\} \mapsto f(\omega)$.

Appendix B.1. AS of the wave propagating transverse in a layer

For the first situation, we consider the AS problem imposed in a 1D domain $\Omega =]0, L[$, with $L = 1$. The 1st order homogenized problem is introduced using (3.21) reduced to 1D with $x = x_1$ and involving the \mathcal{K}_{11}° permeability. The wave amplitude p_1^0 is the solution of the following problem

$$\begin{aligned} i\omega p_1^0 - \mathcal{B}(i\omega) \partial_{xx}^2 p_1^0 &= 0, \quad \text{with } \mathcal{B}(i\omega) = \frac{c_0^2}{\phi_f} \sum_r \frac{X_{11}^r}{i\omega + \eta_r}, \\ p_1^0 &= \bar{p}_\partial \text{ at } x = 0, \\ p_1^0 &= 0 \text{ at } x = L, \end{aligned} \tag{B.1}$$

see (3.17). Using a simplified notation, $p_1 := p_1^0$ the solution of (B.1) is expressed in terms of Fourier series expansion of $\tilde{p}(x)$, as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} p_1(x) &= \bar{p}(x) + \tilde{p}(x), \quad \bar{p}(x) = \bar{p}_\partial(1 - x/L), \\ \tilde{p}(x) &= \sum_k A_k \sin(k\pi x/L), \quad , k = 0, 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned} \tag{B.2}$$

Function $\tilde{p}(x)$ is constituted by fundamental solutions to (B.1) with $\tilde{p} = 0$ at $x = 0$. Constants A_k are determined by the projections of eq. (B.1)₁ in the Fourier basis $\{\sin(k\pi x/L)\}_k$ with $k = 1, 2, \dots$; using

$$\int_0^L \sin(k\pi x/L)(1 - x/L) dx = L/(k\pi), \quad \int_0^L \sin^2(k\pi x/L) dx = L/2, \tag{B.3}$$

the complex coefficients $A_k = \Re A_k + i\Im A_k$ are computed, as follows

$$A_k = -\frac{2i\omega \bar{p}_\partial}{k\pi [i\omega + \mathcal{B}(i\omega)(k\pi/L)^2]}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots \tag{B.4}$$

which defines uniquely the solution $p_1(x)$ given by (B.2). The pressure amplitudes $p_1(x) = p_1^0(x, \omega)$ are then employed in (3.54) to compute $p_2^0(x, \omega)$ with BCs, as follows: $p_2^0(x=0) = 0$ and $p_2^0(x=L) = 0$. The right hand side term can be expressed using the setady streaming seepage velocity $\bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS}(x)$, see (3.54). By virtue of the 1D problem, $\nabla_x \cdot \bar{\mathbf{w}}^{AS} = \partial_x \bar{w}_1^{AS}$, such

that the 2nd order problem describing the AS response to the acoustic field attains the following form: find $p_2(x)$, such that

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathcal{K}}_{11} \partial_{xx}^2 p_2 &= -\partial_x \bar{w}_1^{AS}, \quad p_2(\hat{x}) = 0 \text{ for } \hat{x} = 0, L, \\ \text{where } \bar{w}_1^{AS} &= \sum_{r,k,l} \eta_r^{-1} \beta_1^r \beta_1^k \beta_1^l \mathcal{H}_{kl}^r \sum_{\alpha,\beta=1,2} G_{11}^{\alpha\beta} \overline{\mathcal{M}_{kl}^{\alpha\beta}}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

To solve (B.5), we proceed by the integration of the differential equation while using the boundary condition $p_2(0) = 0$, which yields the ‘‘mean streaming velocity’’, a constant $\bar{c} = \bar{\mathcal{K}}_{11} \partial_x p_2 + \bar{w}_1^{AS}$ involved in the expression for $p_2(x)$,

$$\begin{aligned} p_2(x) &= \bar{\mathcal{K}}_{11}^{-1} \left(\bar{c}x - \int_0^x \bar{w}_1^{AS}(z) dz \right), \\ \text{with } \bar{c} &= L^{-1} \int_0^L \bar{w}_1^{AS}(z) dz. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Note that $\bar{c} = \bar{w}_1^{AS} - w^P$, where $w^P := -\bar{\mathcal{K}}_{11} \partial_x p_2$ is the Darcy flow velocity given by the pressure gradient $\partial_x p_2$. Thus we may conclude that AS effect generate the macroscopic pressure $p_2^0(x)$ which yields the seepage flow w^P compensating the AS source flow \bar{w}_1^{AS} up to a constant. This explains why some authors consider the source \bar{w}_1^{AS} as the ‘‘macroscopic streaming effect’’, Manor (2021).

We shall now give some details on the auxiliary calculations employed to evaluate the expressions in (B.6). In the streaming source term, the only variable depending on $p_1(x)$ is $G_{11}^{\alpha\beta}(x)$ whis is evaluated by (3.29) using $\partial_x P$ and $\partial_x Q$ given, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P(x) &= \bar{p}_\partial (1 - x/L) + \sum_k \Re A_k \sin(k\pi x/L), \quad Q(x) = \sum_k \Im A_k \sin(k\pi x/L), \\ \Rightarrow \\ \partial_x P(x) &= -\bar{p}_\partial / L + \sum_k (k\pi/L) \Re A_k \cos(k\pi x/L), \quad \partial_x Q(x) = \sum_k (k\pi/L) \Im A_k \cos(k\pi x/L), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

To evaluate $G_{11}^{\alpha\beta}$ involved in the expression of \bar{w}_1^{AS} , see (B.5), we need

$$\begin{aligned} G_{11}^{11} &= (\partial_x P(x))^2 = (-\bar{p}_\partial / L + \sum_k (k\pi/L) \Re A_k \cos(k\pi x/L))^2, \\ G_{11}^{22} &= (\partial_x Q(x))^2 = \left(\sum_l (l\pi/L) \Im A_l \cos(l\pi x/L) \right)^2, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

G_{11}^{12} is not needed, since Further, the following functions are employed in the integral of

$G_{11}^{\alpha\beta}$,

$$\begin{aligned} c_{kl}(x) &= \int_0^x \cos(k\pi z/L) \cos(l\pi z/L) dz = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sin(k+l)\pi x/L}{(k+l)\pi/L} + \frac{\sin(k-l)\pi x/L}{(k-l)\pi/L} \right) = c_{lk}(x), \\ d_k(x) &= \int_0^x \cos(k\pi z/L) dz = \frac{L}{k\pi} \sin k\pi x/L. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.9})$$

Thus, using (B.8) and (B.9) we get

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^x G_{11}^{11}(z) dz &= (\bar{p}_\partial/L)^2 x - 2\bar{p}_\partial/L \sum_k (k\pi/L) \Re A_k d_k(x) + \sum_k \sum_l \frac{kl\pi^2}{L^2} \Re A_k \Re A_l c_{kl}(x), \\ \int_0^x G_{11}^{22}(z) dz &= \sum_k \sum_l \frac{kl\pi^2}{L^2} \Im A_k \Im A_l c_{kl}(x), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.10})$$

which enable to compute $p_2(x)$ given in (B.8), whereby, to evaluate \bar{c} , we need (note $c_{kl}(L) = d_k(L) = 0$).

$$\int_0^L G_{11}^{11}(z) dz = \bar{p}_\partial^2/L \quad \text{while} \quad \int_0^L G_{11}^{22} = 0. \quad (\text{B.11})$$

Appendix B.2. AS of the plane wave propagating in infinite porous medium, $x_1 > 0$

For a plane wave in the form (A.7) with $\hat{p}_1^0 = 1$, the steady acoustic streaming source term is expressed using (3.29), such that (recall $\xi = \nu_i x_i$, further $\beta_\nu = \beta_i \nu_i$)

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}^{AS} &= \mathbf{G} : \bar{\mathbf{A}} = \exp\{2\chi_I \xi\} |\chi|^2 \boldsymbol{\nu} \otimes \boldsymbol{\nu} : \bar{\mathbf{A}} \\ &= \exp\{2\chi_I \xi\} |\chi|^2 \bar{\mathbf{A}}_\nu, \quad \bar{\mathbf{A}}_\nu = \sum_{r,k,l} \frac{\beta^r}{\eta^r} \beta_\nu^k \beta_\nu^l \bar{\mathcal{M}}_{kl} \mathcal{H}_{kl}^r, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.12})$$

hence the streaming source divergence becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \bar{w}^{AS} &= 2\chi_I \exp\{2\chi_I \xi\} |\chi|^2 \bar{\mathbf{A}}_\nu, \\ \text{with } \bar{\mathbf{A}}_\nu &= \bar{\mathbf{A}}_\nu \cdot \boldsymbol{\nu} = \sum_{r,k,l} \frac{1}{\eta^r} \beta_\nu^r \beta_\nu^k \beta_\nu^l \bar{\mathcal{M}}_{kl} \mathcal{H}_{kl}^r, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.13})$$

With the reference to (B.5), whereby $\boldsymbol{\nu} = (1, 0, 0)$, hence $\partial_\xi = \partial_{x_1}$, thus $\bar{w}_1^{AS} = \bar{w}_\nu^{AS}$, we shall now consider the halfspace $\xi > 0$ and compute the $p_2(\xi)$ response under the conditions $p_2(\xi = 0) = 0$ and $\partial_\xi p_2(\xi = +\infty) = 0$. Integration of the differential equation arising from (B.5) with the right hand side term $\partial_\xi \bar{w}_\nu^{AS} = \nabla \cdot \bar{w}^{AS}$ given by (B.12) yields

$$\begin{aligned} -\bar{\mathcal{K}}_{\nu\nu} \partial_\xi^2 p_2(\xi) &= 2\chi_I \exp\{2\chi_I \xi\} |\chi|^2 \bar{\mathbf{A}}_\nu(\omega), \\ \text{hence } p_2(\xi) &= -\frac{\bar{\mathbf{A}}_\nu(\omega) |\chi|^2}{\bar{\mathcal{K}}_{\nu\nu} 2\chi_I} (1 - \exp\{2\chi_I \xi\}), \\ w_2^P(\xi) &:= -\bar{\mathcal{K}}_{\nu\nu} \partial_\xi p_2 = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{A}}_\nu(\omega) |\chi|^2}{\bar{\mathcal{K}}_{\nu\nu}} \exp\{2\chi_I \xi\}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.14})$$

so that the $p_2(\xi)$ is growing exponentially with ξ to a plateau, so that the streaming flow velocity decays to zero. Note that $w_2^P = \bar{w}_\nu^{AS}$ in this “1D constraint” problem which does not admit any macroscopic vortex. Hence the AS source directly represents the generated flow.

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